

MAJOR GENERA OF PAPAVERACEAE (POPPY) PLANT FAMILY IN ISRAEL AND PALESTINE. PART I: *FUMARIA* (FUMITORY)

Abdullatif Azab*

*Eastern Plants Company, Box 868, Arara, Israel, 30025.

Article Received on 01 Oct. 2025,
Article Revised on 21 October 2025,
Article Published on 01 Nov. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17473205>

*Corresponding Author

Abdullatif Azab

Eastern Plants Company, Box 868,
Arara, Israel, 30025.

How to cite this Article: Abdullatif Azab. (2025). Major genera of papaveraceae (poppy) plant family in israel and palestine. Part i: *fumaria* (fumitory). World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(21), 344-395.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Fumaria is one of the genera included in the Papaveraceae plant family. All the species of this family have notable alkaloid content, and *Fumaria* alkaloids will be presented and discussed. Traditional medicine used these plants for a variety of purposes. The presence of the *Fumaria* plants in the reviewed region (RR) is very highly debated, and this will be introduced and discussed as well. Modern research studied some of these species extensively but not enough for others. The medicinal properties-activities that were published are of a high diversity, and these will be presented in easy-to-use tables. Significant previous published review articles about *Fumaria* plants of RR will be presented compared with this review article. The structures of most of the natural products that were isolated from these plants will be shown in separate figures. The

indirect products of these plants and some other properties will be introduced in the discussion section.

KEYWORDS: Papaveraceae, *Fumaria*, hepatoprotective, alkaloids, ethnomedicine, chemical composition, *Fumaria officinalis*, *Fumaria parviflora*, review articles, nanoparticles.

ABBREVIATIONS

ABTS 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid), ahc and her/his colleagues, AChE acetylcholine esterase, BHA butylated hydroxyanisole, BHT butylhydroxytoluene, BuChE butyrylcholine esterase, CUPRAC cupric reducing antioxidant capacity, DPPH 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl, DCM dichloromethane, DEE diethyl ether, EO essential oil,

FRAP ferric reducing activity power, GCC general chemical composition, GC-MS gas chromatography mass spectrometry, GPx glutathione peroxidase, HDL high density lipoprotein, HPLC high performance liquid chromatography, LC-MS liquid chromatography mass spectrometry, LDL low density lipoprotein, LPS lipopolysaccharide, MDA malondialdehyde, NI not indicated, NMR nuclear magnetic resonance (spectroscopy), NPs nanoparticles, PBD phosphomolybdenum (assay), PE petroleum ether, RR reviewed region, SOD superoxide dismutase, STZ streptozotocin, TAC total antioxidant capacity, TEAC Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity, TFC total flavonoid content, TG triglycerides, TLC thin layer chromatography, TPC total phenolic content, TTC total tannins content.

1. Taxonomy and Presence of Wild Papaveraceae and *Fumaria* Plants in the RR

Fumaria with Fumitory or Fumewort as common names in English, شاهترج in Arabic and עשנן in Hebrew, is one of the plant genera that comprise the Papaveraceae (Poppy, خشخاشية, פרגיים, English, Arabic, Hebrew, respectively) plant family. According to H-W. Peng *et al.*, this is a medium size plant family that includes about 48 genera and 920 species.^[1] P.C. Gupta *et al.* stated that the *Fumaria* plant genus globally includes about 40 species.^[2]

However, according to the very reliable website of “Flora of Israel and Adjacent Areas” (Israel), in the RR the Papaveraceae plant family includes 9 genera and 38 species. In this series of review articles, three genera will be published: *Fumaria*, *Glaucium* and *Papaver*. This website shows that eleven wild *Fumaria* species are native to the RR, and these are: *Fumaria asepala*, *F. bracteosa*, *F. capreolata*, *F. densiflora*, *F. gaillardotii*, *F. judaica*, *F. kralikii*, *F. macrocarpa*, *F. officinalis*, *F. parviflora*, *F. petteri*.^[3]

But this taxonomy is extremely debated by most notable botanical website: Florapal (Palestine). According to this website, there are no *Fumaria* plants in the reviewed region. Here is a screenshot of this website, section “Species Lists”, letter F, that was taken on the 15th of September 2025, presented as **Figure 1**.^[4]

Figure 1: Screenshot of “Species Lists” of website Florapal, 15/09/2025.

This website was lately published by S. Sallon ahc as “*Florapal* an ethnobotanical website of Flora Palaestina reflects changing patterns of plant use in this region during the mid-20th to 21st century”.^[5] It is clearly not. Moreover, three of the authors of this article co-authored a research article that reported the AChE inhibition activity of Palestinian indigenous flora.^[6] Contradicting the data on Florapal website, in this article three *Fumaria* species are listed, including *F. vaillanti*, which is not included in “Flora of Israel and Adjacent Areas” and consequently, it is not included in our review article.

2. Notable Published Review Articles about *Fumaria* Genus and Species

Our literature search for previously (until 15/09/2025) published review articles about *Fumaria* plant genus and its plants resulted in around twenty five publications. Most of them focus on either *F. officinalis* or *F. parviflora*. A few more review articles present *Fumaria indica* which is not native to the RR. After carefully examining them, we found that fifteen of them are relevant to our review article. These are presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Selected published review articles about *Fumaria* until 15/09/2025.

Author(s)	Pages	References	Major topic(s), Ref.
P.L. Rajagopal ahc	20	62	<i>Fumaria</i> , medicinal activities, no presentation of ethnomedicinal uses and natural products and their structures ^[7]
R. Zhang ahc	18	159	Alkaloids in <i>Fumaria</i> species, comprehensive, detailed lists and structures, brief ethnomedicinal

			presentation ^[8]
F. Kiumarsi & A. R. Derakhshan	17	54	Treatment of gastro and hepatic problems with <i>Fumaria</i> , comprehensive, ethnomedicinal uses and components structures are presented ^[9]
P. Goetz ahc	5	36	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i> , mini review, brief presentation of most relevant topics ^[10]
S. Sajjad ahc	6	53	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i> , mini review, brief presentation of most relevant topics ^[11]
R. Dutta ahc	7	49	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i> , mini review, brief presentation of most relevant topics. No structures of active components ^[12]
A.E. Al-Snafi	9	85	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i> , mini review, brief presentation of most relevant topics. No structures of active components ^[13]
R. Aguiar	8	44	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i> , mini review, brief presentation of most relevant topics. No structures of active components ^[14]
Y. Prokopenko ahc	50	75	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i> , very comprehensive and very detailed ^[15]
S. Kumar ahc	8	42	<i>Fumaria parviflora</i> , mini review, brief presentation of most relevant topics ^[16]
A.E. Al-Snafi	11	83	<i>Fumaria parviflora</i> , medium length review, brief presentation of most relevant topics. No structures of active components ^[17]
P.K. Tayade & M. Jadhav	8	15	<i>Fumaria parviflora</i> , mini review, brief presentation of most relevant topics. No structures of active components ^[18]
F.N. Jamaldeen ahc	14	73	<i>Fumaria parviflora</i> , comprehensive and detailed ^[19]
N. Kumar ahc	5	24	<i>Fumaria parviflora</i> , mini review, brief presentation of most relevant topics ^[20]
A. Sharma ahc	15	77	<i>Fumaria parviflora</i> , comprehensive and detailed ^[21]

3. Ethnobotanical Uses of *Fumaria* Plants of Israel and Palestine

Traditional societies used the *Fumaria* species of the RR for broad range of purposes. Among the eleven species, we found documented (published) frequent uses of four species and a single publication for each one of other three species. It is important to pay attention to the fact that none of these articles was published about traditional uses in the RR. These uses include various treatments of medical problems and for nutritional goals. Summary of this data is presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Ethnobotanical Uses of *Fumaria* Plants of Israel and Palestine.

<i>Fumaria</i> Species	Country; Plant part(s); method(s); use(s); reference
<i>F. asepalata</i>	<p>Iran; leaves; decoction; carminative, Stomach-ache, depurative, against fever [22,28] Aerial parts; powder with Henna; migraine, hand schism, mange [23] Leaves; powder; topical; sores [24] Aerial parts; NI; children jaundice [25] Shoots; NI; migraine, hypertension [26] Whole plant; decoction; eczema, hand chap [27] Whole plant; powder applied externally; itching, skin allergy; decoction; liver diseases; mixed with Henna, hair colour [29] Aerial parts; infusion; head and face itching, allergy, face acne [30] Aerial parts; NI; itching [31] Turkey; flowers; infusion applied externally; fungal infections [32]</p>
<i>F. capreolata</i>	<p>Algeria; NI; NI; bile flow production and flow regulation, stimulation of liver and spleen, worming [33] Aerial parts; decoction, infusion, cream; mainly skin diseases, rarely hypotensive, diuretic [34] Italy; NI; NI but used externally, skin disorders, enhance sweat; purifying digestive system [35] Turkey; aerial parts; NI; bile enhancer, eczema, antifungal [36]</p>
<i>F. gaillardotii</i>	Turkey ; aerial parts; NI; different purposes (no details) [36]
<i>F. judaica</i>	Libya ; NI; NI; diuretic [37]
<i>F. macrocarpa</i>	Greece ; NI; NI; NI but mentioned in the book "About the Antidotes" composed by Nikolaos Myrepsos in 1339 [38]
<i>F. officinalis</i>	<p>Greece; NI; NI; NI but mentioned in the book "About the Antidotes" composed by Nikolaos Myrepsos in 1339 [38] Iran; aerial parts; NI; itching [31] Italy; NI; NI but used externally, skin disorders, enhance sweat; purifying digestive system [35] Morocco; roots, decoction; hyperthyroidism [39] Roots; decoction; diabetes [40] Aerial parts; NI; hypertension, cardiac diseases [41] Pakistan; aerial parts; NI; blood purification, laxative, skin antiallergy [42]</p>
<i>F. parviflora</i>	<p>India; whole plant; NI; fever, influenza, skin itching [43] Iran; whole plant; decoction, poultice; jaundice, skin diseases, allergy, cold, hypertension, coolant, aromatic water [44] NI; NI; jaundice, skin rash, liver detoxification, skin itching [45] Oman; aerial parts; NI; anthelmintic, laxative, skin disorders [46]</p>

4. Published Medicinal Properties-Activities of *Fumaria* Plants of Israel and Palestine

Modern research investigated the medicinal properties-activities of the *Fumaria* species of the RR. But expectedly, some of these plants were notably studied while others were partially or fully "ignored". Modern research confirmed the traditional uses and reported many more. A summary of these findings is shown in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Medicinal Properties-Activities of *Fumaria* Plants of Israel and Palestine.

<i>Fumaria</i> species	Property-Activity, Method, Results, Reference
<i>F. asepalala</i>	<p>Whole plant 80% aqueous methanolic extract were tested for anticancer activity against BEAS-2B, SH-SY5Y, HCT116 and A549 cell lines. Results showed activity against most of these cells.^[47]</p> <p>Whole plant 80% aqueous methanolic extract was tested for antimicrobial (three bacterial and three fungal species), showing activity only against one of them.^[48]</p> <p>Leaves and stems ethanolic extract was tested for antibacterial activity against <i>S. aureus</i>, <i>B. cereus</i>, <i>E. coli</i>, <i>P. aeruginosa</i>. Results were moderate to high activity.^[49]</p> <p>Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species. The links between single alkaloids and single species are not indicated. These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50]</p> <p>Fruits, leaves, roots and stems were separately extracted with 96% aqueous ethanol and the resulting extracts were chromatographed yielding alkaloid fractions. These fractions were tested for antifungal activity. Results showed high efficiency, and the effect was due to genetic influence. The major alkaloids that were isolated are Protopine, Sanguinarine, Parfumine and Allocryptopine (Figure 2).^[51]</p> <p>Aerial parts were separately extracted with methanol and ethyl acetate, and the extracts were tested for antioxidant activity, using DPPH, superoxide anion scavenging and lipid peroxidation methods. Both extracts showed high activities.^[52]</p> <p>Whole plant ethanolic extract was chromatographed affording Protopine, Allocryptopine and Sanguinarine, in addition to Cryptopine, Stylophine, Scoulerine and Bicuculline (Figure 2).^[53]</p> <p>Whole plant methanol-chloroform (1:1) extract had significant enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE) activity.^[54]</p> <p>Whole plant methanolic extract had significant enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE and carbonic anhydrase I and II) activity.^[55]</p> <p>Aerial parts EO (hydrodistillation) was tested for antimicrobial (against five bacterial strains and <i>Candida albicans</i>) and antioxidant (TAC method) activities, showing significant results in both tests. EO was analyzed (GC-MS) and the major components were (%): thymol 20.42, benzyl benzoate 15.89, phytol 20.74 and Hexahydrofarnesyl acetone (Figure 2) 12.92.^[56]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic extract had moderate antimicrobial activity against seven bacterial species and <i>C. albicans</i>.^[57]</p>
<i>F. bracteosa</i>	<p>Whole plant alkaloid extract was chromatographed yielding Protopine and Bicuculline (Figure 2), in addition to Adlumidine (optical isomer of Bicuculline) and Hydrastine (Figure 3).^[58]</p>
<i>F. capreolata</i>	<p>Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species (see <i>F. asepalala</i>). These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50]</p>

	<p>Whole plant ethanolic extract was chromatographed affording Protopine, Sanguinarine, Cryptopine, Stylophine, Scoulerine and Bicuculline (Figure 2), in addition to Fumaritine, Capnoidine and Coptisine (Figure 4A).^[53]</p> <p>Whole plant methanol-chloroform (1:1) extract had significant enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE) activity.^[54]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic extract had analgesic (acetic acid writhing test) and anti-inflammatory (xylene or 12-O-tetradecanoylphorbol-13-acetate-induced) activities in mice.^[59]</p> <p>Aerial parts alkaloid extract had anti-inflammatory activity against dinitrobenzene sulfonic acid-induced colitis, <i>in vitro</i> (intestinal epithelial CMT93 cells) and <i>in vivo</i> (mice). Effect was measured with several biomarkers. The extract was analyzed (liquid chromatography) and the main alkaloids were (mg/g): Parfumine 3.18, Protopine 9.27, Stylophine 12.67 (Figure 2), and Isoboldine 4.5, Coreximine 2.32, Cheilanthifoline 3.04, Dehydrocheilanthifoline 0.69, Fumariline 1.18, Coptisine 11.04, Corysamine 0.88 (Figure 4A).^[60]</p> <p>Follow up of previous research: aerial parts alkaloid extract had anti-inflammatory activity against dextran sodium sulfate-induced colitis in mice. Effect was measured with several biomarkers.^[61]</p> <p>Earlier study by the same research group: aerial parts alkaloid extract had anti-inflammatory activity against LPS-induced inflammation in RAW 264.7 cells. It also had antinociceptive activity tested by acetic acid-induced writhing and formalin-induced paw licking methods. Each effect was measured with several biomarkers.^[62]</p> <p>Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract had anti-inflammatory activity against carrageenan-induced inflammation in mice. Partial GCC is presented.^[63]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was tested for antioxidant activity using DPPH, FRAP and linoleic acid peroxidation methods. The methanolic extract was analyzed with GC-MS resulting the detection of significant amounts (%) of five alkaloids: Protopine 50.6, Stylophine 22.9, Fumariline 8, Fumaritine 3.7 in addition to Fumaricine 2, Protoberberine 3.2 and Fumarofine (traces). (Figure 4A).^[64]</p> <p>Aerial parts 90% aqueous ethanolic extract was analyzed for TPC and tested for antioxidant activity (DPPH, FRAP and β-carotene bleaching methods; with BHA, BHT and ascorbic acid as reference antioxidants). Fresh and dry plant material as well as the extract were analyzed for GCC.^[66]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was tested for antioxidant activity using ABTS, DPPH, FRAP and hydrogen peroxide scavenging methods. It was also tested for acute toxicity in mice and erythrocytes resulting no toxicity in both tests.^[67]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract had ameliorative antiulcer activity in acetic acid-induced colitis in mice.^[68]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was fractionized and analyzed affording eleven alkaloids: Pallidine, N-methylcoclaurine, Reticuline, "Simple Isoquinoline", Magnoflorine (Figure 4B), Sanguinarine, Protopine, Scoulerine, Isoboldine, Dehydrocheilanthifoline and Coptisine. In addition, choline was also isolated.^[69]</p> <p>Whole plant ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding</p>
--	--

	<p>nine previously known alkaloids (%): Protopine 0.11, Cryptopine 0.09, Allocryptopine 0.09, Fumaritine 0.1, Stylopine 0.09, Scoulerine 0.05, Coptisine 0.05, Capnoidine 0.12, and Sanguinarine 0.05.^[70]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding nine previously known alkaloids (%): Isoboldine 4, Sanguinarine 2, Bicuculline 2, Protopine 45, Fumariline 4, Parfumine 12, Cheilanthifoline 5, Scoulerine 4 and Stylopine 6.^[71]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed with GC-MS yielding six previously known alkaloids (% of total alkaloid content): Fumarophycine 2 and Dihydrosanguinarine 2 (Figure 4B), in addition to Protopine 71, Stylopine 10, Parfumine 5 and Fumariline 11.^[72]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was qualitatively analyzed with GC-MS yielding eight previously known alkaloids: Protopine, Protoberberine, Stylopine, Fumariline, Fumarophycine, Fumaritine, Fumarofine and Fumaricine.^[73]</p> <p>Aerial parts were extracted for alkaloids using methanol-DCM (1:1) and the extract was comparatively and qualitatively analyzed with two methods yielding 24 precisely identified compounds: N,N-dimethylcoclaurine, Coclaurine, Demethyleneberberine, Jatrorubine, Impatien C, 8-Oxocoptisine (Figure 4B), in addition to Pallidine, Fumaritine, N-methylcoclaurine, Magnoflorine, Reticuline, Parfumine, Parfumidine, Isoboldine, Coreximine, Cheilanthifoline, Dehydrocheilanthifoline, Cryptopine, Protopine, Fumariline, Stylopine, Coptisine, Corysamine, Dihydrosanguinarine.^[74]</p> <p>Fruits 60% ethanolic extract had moderate AChE inhibition activity and no antioxidant activity (DPPH method).^[6]</p> <p>Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was analyzed for TFC, TPC and total hydroxycinnamic acids content. It was also analyzed (HPLC-MS) for phenolic components where six known compounds were detected. The extract had notable antioxidant (ABTS and TEAC methods) and diuretic (in saline-loaded rats) activities.^[75]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic extract had anticancer (against human hepatocellular carcinoma cancer cell lines Hep3B and HepG2) and antioxidant (DPPH and PBD methods) activities.^[76]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic extract was partially analyzed for alkaloids and phenolic acids. Crude extracts and five of its components (Fumarophycine, <i>O</i>-Methylfumarophycine, Protopine, Caffeic acid and Protocatechuic acid) were tested for antioxidant activity, using DPPH and lipid peroxidation methods.^[86]</p> <p>a) The presented structure of Fumarofine in this article is mistaken^[65]</p>
<i>F. densiflora</i>	<p>Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species (see <i>F. asepala</i>). These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50]</p> <p>Whole plant methanol-chloroform (1:1) extract had significant enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE, in high dose) activity.^[54]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed with GC-MS yielding six previously known alkaloids (% of total alkaloid content): Sinactine 2 and Adlumine 3 (Figure 5A), in addition to Protopine 76, Cryptopine 8, Parfumine 5 and Dihydrosanguinarine 6.^[72]</p>

	<p>Leaves 60% ethanolic extract had high AChE inhibition and antioxidant (DPPH method) activities.^[6]</p> <p>Twenty-two alkaloids were isolated from aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract. Two of these alkaloids, Parfumine and Fumaritine, had dose-dependent effect on isolated perfused mouse heart and ilium. Two alkaloids were isolated for the first time from a natural source, N-methyl-5-hydroxystylopine chloride and Fumaricine N-oxide; Norfumaritin was isolated for the second time from natural source, and Norjuziphine was isolated for the first time from this plant (Figure 5A).^[77]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed affording eight alkaloids, one of them was new, Densiflorine (Figure 5A).^[78]</p> <p>Whole plant ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding fourteen previously known compounds: N-methylhydrasteine, Fumaridine, Adlumidine (Figure 5A); in addition to Protopine, Hydrastine, Parfumine, Fumaritine, Cheilanthifoline, Cryptopine, Fumariline, Parfumidine, Scoulerine, Isosalutaridine (Pallidine), and Bicuculline.^[79]</p> <p>Whole plant ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed affording Fumadensine, Fumaramine, Adlumidiceine (Figure 5A), Palmatine (Figure 5B), in addition to Coptisine, Sinactine, Protopine, Cryptopine and Densiflorine.^[80]</p> <p>Flowering aerial parts methanolic extract had gastroprotective activity in on primary cultures of rat hepatocytes intoxicated with CCl₄. This effect is associated with the alkaloids contained in the extract. Analysis of the extract afforded twenty alkaloids where 18 were previously presented, in addition to Fumaritridine, Corytuberine, Fumaflorine (and its methyl ester) and <i>cis-N</i>-methylstylopinium iodide (Figure 5B).^[81]</p> <p>Interestingly, the same research group published a year after the previous article, the isolation of Fumaflorine as a new compound.^[82]</p> <p>Whole plant 85% aqueous ethanolic extract was fractionized with PE, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol. The crude extract and fractions were analyzed for TFC and TPC. They also had significant antioxidant activity (DPPH, FRAP, Fe⁺² chelating, xanthine oxidase inhibition methods).^[83]</p> <p>Aerial parts 85% aqueous ethanolic extract was tested for antiparasitic activity (against malarial <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> and human African trypanosomiasis <i>Trypanosoma bruceirhodesiense</i>). It was also partially analyzed (HPLC) for phenolic acid composition.^[84]</p> <p>Whole plant was separately extracted with <i>n</i>-hexane, ethyl acetate, ethanol, methanol and water. The extracts were tested for toxicity against Brine shrimp (<i>Artemia salina</i>), and the <i>n</i>-hexane and ethyl acetate extracts were toxic.^[85]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic extract was partially analyzed for alkaloids and phenolic acids. Crude extracts and five of its components (Fumarophycine, <i>O</i>-Methylfumarophycine, Protopine, Caffeic acid and Protocatechuic acid) were tested for antioxidant activity, using DPPH and lipid peroxidation methods.^[86]</p>
F. gaillardoti	Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species (see <i>F. asepala</i>). These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and

	<p>antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50] Whole plant ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed affording: N-methylhydrastine (Figure 6), in addition to Protopine, Fumaritine, Fumaricine, Stylophine and Bicuculline.^[87]</p>
<i>F. judaica</i>	<p>Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species (see <i>F. asepala</i>). These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50] Whole plant methanol-chloroform (1:1) extract had significant enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE) activity.^[54] Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding Stylophine, Cheilanthifoline, Coptisine, Protopine, Parfumine and Bicuculline.^[88] Whole plant ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed affording (%): Protopine 0.18, Adlumidine 0.17, Allocryptopine 0.11, Stytopine 0.11, Fumaritine 0.07, Coptisine 0.04 and Scoulerine 0.03.^[89]</p>
<i>F. kralikii</i>	<p>Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species (see <i>F. asepala</i>). These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50] Whole plant methanol-chloroform (1:1) extract had significant enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE) activity.^[54] Whole plant 85% aqueous ethanolic extract was fractionized with PE, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol. The crude extract and fractions were analyzed for TFC and TPC. They also had significant antioxidant activity (DPPH, FRAP, Fe⁺² chelating, xanthine oxidase inhibition methods).^[83] Aerial parts 85% aqueous ethanolic extract was tested for antiparasitic activity (against malarial <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> and human African trypanosomiasis <i>Trypanosoma bruceirhodesiense</i>). It was also partially analyzed (HPLC) for phenolic acid composition.^[84] Leaves ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding a new compound, Norfumaritine (Figure 7), which is the demethylation product of Fumaritine.^[90] Aerial parts (plants were collected from three different locations) ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed affording Stylophine, Sinactine, Chelanthifoline, Scoulerine, Protopine, Cryptopine, Dihydrofumariline, Fumaricine, Parfumidine, Fumaritine, Fumariline, Parfumine, Fumarofine, Fumarophycine, <i>O</i>-methylfumarophycine and Dihydrosanguinarine.^[91] Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was tested for antioxidant activity using ABTS, CUPRAC, DPPH and FRAP methods. It was analyzed for TFC, TPC and phenolic composition where ten known compounds were detected.^[92] Aerial parts methanolic extract was fractionized with chloroform and water. The combined polar fractions were analyzed using GC-MS detecting 8 monosaccharides, 5 organic (non-amino) acids, 5 lipids and 8 amino acids. The structure of Threonic acid is shown in Figure 7.^[93] Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding Protopine, Fumarophycine, Berberine, Adlumidicine,</p>

	Coptisine, <i>O</i> -methylfumarophycine, Cryptopine, Stylophine, and Canadine (Figure 7). ^[152]
<i>F. macrocarpa</i>	<p>Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species (see <i>F. asepala</i>). These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50]</p> <p>Whole plant methanol-chloroform (1:1) extract had significant enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE) activity.^[54]</p> <p>Whole plant ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed affording (%) Protopine 0.16, Sinactine 0.13, Adlumine 0.13. Cryptopine 0.11, Fumariline 0.11 and Coptisine 0.07.^[94]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed yielding Fumariline, Parfumine and Bicuculline.^[95]</p>
<i>F. officinalis</i>	<p>Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species (see <i>F. asepala</i>). These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed with GC-MS yielding nine previously known alkaloids (% of total alkaloid content): Sinactine 6, Adlumine 2, Protopine 42, Cryptopine 11, Parfumine 3, Fumariline 3, Fumarophycine 24, Fumaritine 6 and Dihydrosanguinarine 2.^[72]</p> <p>Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was analyzed for TFC, TPC and total hydroxycinnamic acids content. It was also analyzed (HPLC-MS) for phenolic components where seven known compounds were detected. The extract had notable antioxidant (ABTS and TEAC methods) and diuretic (in saline-loaded rats) activities.^[75]</p> <p>Flowering aerial parts methanolic extract had gastroprotective activity in on primary cultures of rat hepatocytes intoxicated with CCl_4. This effect is associated with the alkaloids contained in the extract.^[81]</p> <p>Whole plant was separately extracted with <i>n</i>-hexane, ethyl acetate, ethanol, methanol and water. The extracts were tested for toxicity against Brine shrimp (<i>Artemia salina</i>), and the <i>n</i>-hexane extract was toxic.^[85]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic extract was partially analyzed for alkaloids and phenolic acids. Crude extracts and five of its components (Fumarophycine, <i>O</i>-Methylfumarophycine, Protopine, Caffeic acid and Protocatechuic acid) were tested for antioxidant activity, using DPPH and lipid peroxidation methods.^[86]</p> <p>Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was tested for antioxidant activity using ABTS, CUPRAC, DPPH and FRAP methods. It was analyzed for TFC, TPC and phenolic composition where ten known compounds were detected.^[92]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic extract was fractionized with chloroform and water. The combined polar fractions were analyzed using GC-MS detecting 8 monosaccharides, 5 organic (non-amino) acids, 7 lipids and 10 amino acids.^[93]</p> <p>Leaves were separately extracted with PE, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol. The extracts were tested for antioxidant activity using superoxide scavenging method (reference: ascorbic acid). The</p>

antiasthmatic activity of ethyl acetate and methanolic extracts was tested using two methods: histamine-induced in guinea pig ileum and acetyl choline in guinea pig trachea. The **anti-inflammatory** activity of these two extracts was tested against ovalbumin-induced inflammation in the animals. **Acute toxicity** and ***in vivo* antioxidant** (measured with three biomarkers) activities of the methanolic extract were measured in the same animals.^[96]

Leaves were separately extracted with 70% aqueous ethanol and water, and the extracts were analyzed for TFC, TPC and TTC. They were tested for **anticancer** (against MCF-7 cancer cells), **antibacterial** (against ten bacterial strains), **antioxidant** (using DPPH and PBD methods), **anti-inflammatory** (haemoglobin denaturation) and **antidiabetic** (haemoglobin glycosylation) activities. The extracts were analyzed for phenolic composition yielding known compounds. Leaves were also extracted for total alkaloid content.^[97]

Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was analyzed for GCC. It had **antihyperlipidemic** activity in high fat diet-induced in rats. Effect was measured with five biomarkers.^[98]

Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was tested for **antidiabetic** (alloxan-induced in mice), **anti-inflammatory** (carrageenan-induced) activities, with a proposed mechanism of action. Authors refer these activities to most active components of the extract, Stylophine and Sanguinarine.^[99]

Aerial parts were separately extracted with *n*-hexane, chloroform, methanol and water, and GCCs of these extracts were determined. The **antioxidant** activity was tested using DPPH method. The **antidiabetic** activity was tested *in vivo* (alloxan-induced in rats) and *in vitro* (α -amylase inhibition).^[100]

Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed affording 17 compounds including Jatrorrhizine (**Figure 8**). The extract was tested for **anti-inflammatory** activity using two methods. *In vivo* (against carrageenan-induced paw edema in mice, and *in vitro* (bovine serum albumin denaturation). The alkaloids were tested *in silico* (molecular docking) resulting highest possible potency in Protopine, Bicuculline, Stylophine (highest), and coptisine.^[101]

Aerial parts 60% aqueous ethanolic extract was defatted with PE and partitioned with ethyl acetate yielding flavonoid-rich fraction. This fraction was tested for **antioxidant** (lipid peroxidation method) and **anti-inflammatory** (bovine serum albumin denaturation) activities. The **nephroprotective** activity was tested against permethrin-induced kidney damage in rats.^[102]

Whole plant was separately extracted with chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol. The extracts were tested for **antibacterial** activity against twelve bacterial strains resulting no effect.^[103]

Aerial parts aqueous extract was analyzed for TPC and phenolic composition where caffeic and rosmarinic acids were the major components. The extract was tested for **antimicrobial** (against seven microbial species, showing moderate effect against four) and **antioxidant** (using ABTS and DPPH methods) activities.^[104]

Aerial parts 95% aqueous ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was partitioned

with several solvents, and the crude extract and the fractions were analyzed for total alkaloid content. They were tested for **antibacterial** (against three bacterial species) and **antioxidant** (using six methods) activities. The crude extract was analyzed (GC-MS) for alkaloid composition detecting: Protopine 34.48%, Bicuculline 18.63%, Cryptopine 6.70%, Sinactine, Adlumine, Fumaritine, Fumariline, Stylophine, Parfumine, Fumarophycine and Corlumine (**Figure 8**).^[105] Leaves were separately extracted with PE, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol, and the extracts were analyzed for GCC, TFC and TPC. They were tested for **antioxidant** activity using DPPH and hydrogen peroxide scavenging methods, with ascorbic acid as reference.^[106] Flowering aerial parts were extracted with 70% aqueous ethanol using three methods: maceration, ultrasound-assisted and microwave-assisted. The **antioxidant** capacity of the extract was tested using ABTS, CUPRAC, DPPH and FRAP methods. Microwave-assisted extracts were most potent.^[107] Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was analyzed for TFC, TPC and partial chemical composition using HPLC. The extract was tested for **antioxidant** (DPPH method), **antiulcer** (ethanol-induced gastric ulcer and gastric acid secretion in rats) and **acute toxicity** (rats) activities. Molecular docking was performed for four phenolic compounds contained in the extract with three synthetic reference molecules.^[108] Leaves were successively extracted with PE, chloroform and methanol. The combined extracts were analyzed for GCC and tested for **antioxidant** activity using DPPH method. The **antiaging** activity was tested *in vitro* (enzyme inhibition: hyaluronidase, collagenase and elastase) and *in vivo* (topical cream application in skin irritation and UV light exposure in mice).^[109] Leaves ethanolic extract had **Immunoprotective** activity in ethanol-induced immunosuppression in mice and in cells. Effect was measured by several biomarkers including oxidative-antioxidative.^[110] Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract had **antitoxicity** effect against fluoxetine-induced testicular damage in male rats. Effect was measured with several physical and histological biomarkers.^[111] Fruits ethanolic extract had **aphrodisiac** effect in female rats, where effect was measured by frequency of sexual activity. In addition, extract GCC is presented.^[112] Whole plants alkaloid extract was obtained using ion exchange method. The crude extract and its components (Protopine, Cryptopine, Fumaritine, Sanguinarine, Sinactine, and Stylophine) had **anti-arrhythmic** activity in mice and rabbits. Quinidine and Ethmosine were used as standard drugs.^[113] Mineral composition (13 elements) was tested by a list of complete results is not presented.^[114] Aerial parts were separately extracted for alkaloids and phenolics and both extracts were chromatographed yielding previously known compounds, five alkaloids and eight phenolics.^[115] Aerial parts 95% ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed affording 20 compounds: two new compounds, Fumaranine, and Fumarostrejdine, and three previously known that were not presented so

	<p>far in this article, O-methylfumarofine, N-methylcorydaldine and Corydamine (Figure 8). All others are presented in the other figures. All the alkaloids were tested for enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE and prolyl oligopeptidase) where ten compounds were active.^[116]</p> <p>Aerial parts were successively extracted with PE, chloroform and ethanol. The ethanolic extract was tested for hepatoprotective activity in carbon tetrachloride-induced rats, showing good results. The three extracts were analyzed for GGC, but results are not reported. In addition, the article uses wrong term of “photochemical screening” instead of “phytochemical screening”.^[117]</p> <p>Leaves were separately extracted with 70% aqueous ethanol and pure methanol. Both extracts were tested for antiparasitic activity against adult <i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>, <i>Fasciola hepatica</i>, and <i>Echinostoma caproni</i> in vitro. The hydroethanolic extract had weak activity while the methanolic was inactive.^[118]</p> <p>Plant part, alcohol name and alcohol concentration are not reported, but the resulting extract/s had positive effect on rabbits’ kidneys.^[119]</p> <p>Aerial parts were successively extracted with PE, chloroform and ethanol. The ethanolic extract was tested for acute toxicity in mice (not toxic) and for muscle relaxation in stressed rats. The stress was induced by rota rod and traction tests, and positive effect was indicated in both. Very partial GCCs of the three extracts are reported.^[120]</p> <p>Whole plant 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was used to prepare a cream in combination with silymarin, and this cream had anti-moderate-eczema activity in human patients.^[121]</p> <p>Aerial parts were extracted with 50 and 70% aqueous ethanol, and these extracts were analyzed for TFC, TTC and total alkaloid content. The skin protection of these extracts was tested in keratinocyte model resulting positive effect. Antioxidant activity was tested with ABTS, CUPRAC, DPPH, FRAP and H₂O₂ scavenging methods. Extracts were also analyzed for chemical compositions resulting 21 phenolics.^[122]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was prepared in basic, neutral and acidic forms. The three extracts were tested for acute toxicity in mice resulting slight effect.^[123]</p>
<p><i>F. parviflora</i></p>	<p>Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species (see <i>F. asepala</i>). These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50]</p> <p>Whole plant methanol-chloroform (1:1) extract had significant enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE) activity.^[54]</p> <p>Whole plant methanolic extract had moderate antimicrobial activity against seven bacterial species and <i>C. albicans</i>.^[57]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed with GC-MS yielding eight previously known alkaloids (% of total alkaloid content): Parfumidine 7 (Figure 9A), in addition to Sinactine 2, Adlumine 3, Protopine 57, Cryptopine 5, Parfumine 14, Fumariline 10, and Dihydrosanguinarine 2.^[72]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic extract had anticancer (against human hepatocellular carcinoma cancer cell lines Hep3B and HepG2) and antioxidant (DPPH and PBD methods) activities.^[76]</p>

Whole plant 85% aqueous ethanolic extract was fractionized with PE, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol. The crude extract and fractions were analyzed for TFC and TPC. They also had significant **antioxidant** activity (DPPH, FRAP, Fe⁺² chelating, xanthine oxidase inhibition methods).^[83]

Aerial parts 85% aqueous ethanolic extract was tested for **antiparasitic** activity (against malarial *Plasmodium falciparum* and human African trypanosomiasis *Trypanosoma bruceirhodesiense*). It was also partially analyzed (HPLC) for phenolic acid composition.^[84]

Aerial parts methanolic extract was partially analyzed for alkaloids and phenolic acids. Crude extracts and five of its components (Fumarophycine, *O*-Methylfumarophycine, Protopine, Caffeic acid and Protocatechuic acid) were tested for **antioxidant** activity, using DPPH and lipid peroxidation methods.^[86]

Flowers, leaves, stems and roots were separately extracted with water and the extracts were applied for **allelopathic** activity against *Lolium rigidum*. Leaves extract was most active.^[124]

Whole plant was tested for **anticancer** activity against MCF-7 cancer cells, showing moderate effect. The extract was chromatographed yielding 19 compounds. Molecular docking was performed for these components resulting highest potency for Bidentlignasides A and B. Structures of eight of the isolated compounds (Berberine, Bidentlignaside A, Bidentlignaside B, Bowdichione, Friedelin-3,4-lactone, Stepharanine, Syringaresinol and Tembatarine), including Bidentlignasides A and B are shown in **Figure 9A**.^[125]

Aerial parts methanolic extract had **antidiabetic** activity in STZ-induced diabetic rats. Effect was measured with several biomarkers especially blood glucose concentrations.^[126]

Whole plant *n*-butanol extract had **antidiabetic** activity in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. Effect was measured with several biomarkers mainly blood glucose levels.^[127]

Hydroalcoholic extract had positive effect in type II diabetics.^[128,129]

Leaves 96% aqueous ethanolic extract had **antidiabetic** (in STZ-induced diabetic rats) and **hepatoprotective** activities. Effects were measured by blood lipids (cholesterol, HDL, LDL, TG) and oxidative stress biomarkers (SOD, GPx, MDA).^[130]

Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract had **antihyperlipidemic** activity in high fat-fed rats.^[131]

Whole plant 70% aqueous ethanolic extract had **anti-inflammatory** effect in carrageenan-induced paw edema in rats.^[132]

Leaves aqueous and ethanolic extracts had **anti-inflammatory** activities in rats. Inflammation was induced by carrageenan (paw) and cotton pallet (granuloma). Effects were measured with several parameters, especially inflammatory biomarkers.^[133]

Whole plant 50% aqueous methanolic extract had **antimicrobial** (against four bacterial strains, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, *E. faecalis*, and four fungal species, *C. albicans*, *A. niger*, *C. lunata*, *A. alternata*). It also had **antioxidant** activity (DPPH method).^[134]

Aerial parts 70% aqueous methanolic extract had **antibacterial** (against five species) and **antioxidant** (DPPH method) activities. Analysis of the

extract using GC-MS afforded 21 compounds where the major component was 4H-pyran-4-one (**Figure 9A**), 13.26%.^[135]

Flowers, leaves, roots and stems were separately extracted with *n*-hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol (16 extracts). All extracts were tested for **antibacterial** (seven species) activity.^[136]

Whole plant methanolic extract was chromatographed and a new compound was isolated and characterized: *n*-Octacosan-7-ol (**Figure 9A**), which is mistakenly named N-octacosan-7 β -ol in the article title. This compound was tested for **antimicrobial** (against four bacterial and two fungal strains), **antiparasitic** (against *Leishmania donovani*) activity. Its **cytotoxicity** was tested on mammalian macrophages isolated from mice (nontoxic).^[137]

Whole plant methanolic extract had **antinociceptive** activity tested with formalin and hot plate tests, in rats. **Acute toxicity** test (mice) showed that the extract was relatively nontoxic (indomethacin reference).^[138]

Fruits, leaves, roots and stems were separately extracted with ethanol and the four extracts were analyzed for TFC and TPC. The **antioxidant** activities of the extracts were tested with DPPH method.^[139]

Whole plant aqueous extract had **antioxidant** activity tested with DPPH and H₂O₂ scavenging methods, and **hepatoprotective** activity against CCl₄-induced liver damage in rats.^[140]

Whole plant 96% aqueous ethanolic extract had protective effect **against oxidative stress** and **testis tissue damage** in STZ-induced diabetic male rats. Each one of the effects was measured using three different parameters.^[141]

Whole plant aqueous and ethanolic extracts were tested for **antiparasitic** activity against gastrointestinal nematodes of sheep. Tests were performed *in vitro* (eggs) and *in vivo* (larvae).^[142]

Roots and stems were separately extracted with *n*-hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol, and the eight extracts were analyzed for GCC. Each one of the extracts was tested for **antiparasitic** effect against southern root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita*. Test were performed *in vitro* (eggs) and *in vivo* (nematodes on the plants).^[143]

Whole plant aqueous extract had **antiparasitic** (antileishmanial) activity, *in vitro* (promastigotes, uninfected/infected macrophages with amastigotes) and *in vivo* (infected mice).^[144]

Whole plant ethanolic extract had **antiparasitic** (against *Leishmania major*) separately on in synergistic effect with Amphotericin B. Effect was tested *in vitro* (standard strain) and *in vivo* (infected mice). Expression of miR146a-5p and miR499 levels were the major biomarkers measured to detect the effect of treatment.^[145]

Aerial parts had **antiparasitic** effect against *Fasciola* species in naturally infected buffaloes.^[146]

Whole plant *n*-hexane extract was chromatographed resulting the isolation and characterization of Nonacosane-10-ol and 23a-Homostigmast-5-en-3 β -ol (**Figure 9A**). These compounds had **antiparasitic** activity against *Meloidogyne incognita*. The effect was tested *in vitro* (eggs) and *in vivo* (juveniles).^[147]

Leaves ethanolic extract had **antitoxicity** activity against lead-induced testicular damage in male rats. Effect was measured with oxidative stress

biomarkers (GPx, MDA, SOD), and sperm parameters. ^[148]

Aerial parts were successively extracted with PE DEE, benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and 95% aqueous ethanol. The combined extracts were chromatographed affording, among other compounds *n*-Pentatriacontane, CH₃(CH₂)₃₃CH₃. In addition, inorganic salts and fumaric acid contents were determined. ^[149]

Whole plant ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding 35 alkaloids, where three of them were new: Fumaramidine, Fumariflorine and Parviflorine (**Figure 9B**). ^[150]

Follow up of previous study resulted the isolation of a new alkaloid, the enantiomer of Corlumine presented in **Figure 8**. Seven previously known alkaloids were also isolated. ^[151]

Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding Protopine, Adlumidicine, Dihydrofumariline, Parfumine, Fumariline, Cryptopine, Stylophine, 8-Oxocoptisine, Sanguinarine, Coptisine, In addition, Oxysanguinarine (**Figure 9B**) was also isolated from this species for the first time. ^[152]

Leaves and twigs of cultivated plant methanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed affording Rhoegenine (**Figure 9B**) and other previously known alkaloids. ^[153]

Fumaric acid content in various parts of the plant was determined. ^[154]

Aerial parts EO (hydrodistillation) was analyzed using GC-MS yielding 29 compounds, and the five major components (%) were: 3-Isothujopsanone 5, Farnesyl acetate 8 (**Figure 9B**), in addition to Octadecane 13.2, Hexadecanoic acid 23.2 and Methyl-9,12-octadecadionate 7.5. ^[155]

Aerial parts methanolic extract was chromatographed affording five new compounds (**Figure 9B**): (5 α H,11 α H)-8-oxo-homoiridolide (Comp. 1), *n*-docosanyl-2-*O*- β -*D*-glucopyranosyl salicylate (Comp. 2), 2-methyl-6-hydroxymethylenedodecan-10-oyl-12,15-olide-14-*O*- β -*D*-xylopyranoside (Comp. 3), 4-oxo-stigmast-5-en-3 β -ol-*D*-glucopyranoside (Comp. 4) and salicylic acid-*O*- β -*D*-xylopyranoside (Comp. 5). Several previously known were also isolated. ^[156]

Whole plant contents of Protopine and β -Sitosterol were determined. ^[157]

Follow up of the research cited as reference 156: whole plant methanolic extract was chromatographed affording six new compounds (**Figure 9B**). Several previously known were also isolated. ^[158]

Authors of this publication claim that they isolated “new flavonoids” from the aerial parts 85% aqueous methanolic extract. Practically, they presented only one as such: kaempferol-3-*O*-rhamnoside. ^[159] This compound was isolated many years before this research and numerous articles were published about its isolation, activities and uses. See ^[160]

These articles reported TFC, TPC and/or GCC. ^[161,162]

Whole plant methanolic extract was analyzed affording three new compounds (**Figure 9C**): *n*-propyl-3,4-dioxymethylene benzene (comp. 1), 5 β , 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 β -hexahydrocoumarin (comp.2) and 2,6-dimethyl dodecan-10-oyl-12,15-olide (comp. 3). Several previously known were also isolated. ^[163] *

* In the title of this article, it is stated that aerial parts were extracted, but in the experimental section it is clearly written that the whole plant was used.

Whole plant/aerial parts 80%/90% aqueous ethanolic extract had **Hepatoprotective** activity against CCl_4 -induced damages in rat liver.

Effect was measured with several biomarkers, especially oxidant-antioxidant. Silymarin was positive control.^[164,165,166]

Leaves 70% aqueous methanolic extract was tested for

Hepatoprotective activity against Isoniazid and Rifampicin-induced liver injury in Rats. Silymarin was reference. Effect was measured with five parameters. Extract **acute toxicity** was tested and found nontoxic.^[167]

Aerial parts 80% aqueous ethanolic extract had **hepatoprotective** activity against vincristine-induced hepatotoxicity in male rats. Effect was measured with oxidant-antioxidant biomarkers.^[168]

Whole plant 95% aqueous methanolic extract was tested for

Hepatoprotective activity against Isoniazid and Rifampicin-induced liver injury in Rats. Effect was measured with five parameters.^[169]

Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract had **hepatoprotective** activity against high fat-induced liver damages in rats. Effect was measured with eight parameters, mainly blood lipid levels.^[170]

Whole plant 80% aqueous ethanolic extract had **hepatoprotective** activity on carbon tetrachloride-treated HepG2 cells. Effect was measured with several parameters, mainly cell viability.^[171]

Aerial parts aqueous extract was tested in breastfeeding infants for **anti-colic** activity in comparison with Simethicone, where the extract had stronger effect, that was measured with several parameters like crying, stooling, constipation, diarrhea and regurgitation. The extract was also analyzed for fumaric acid content.^[172]

Aerial parts 70% aqueous methanolic extract had **prokinetic** and **laxative** activities in mice, and **spasmodic** effect in guinea pig isolated ileum but not in rabbit isolated ileum. Carbachol was reference drug and atropine was used to block the spasmodic effect in order to study the mechanism of action.^[173]

Whole plant encapsulated powder was administered to haemodialysis patients for **treatment** of **Uremic Pruritus**, compared with Gabapentin.^[174]

Whole plant powder was administered to haemodialysis patients for **treatment** of **Uremic Pruritus**, compared with Gabapentin. Effects of both treatments were approximately equal.^[175]

Whole plant 50% aqueous ethanolic extract had **preservative** activity in stored *Rutilus kutum*. Effect was measured with various parameters, textural and chemical, mainly oxidant-antioxidant.^[176]

Whole plant methanolic extract had positive effects on **spermatogenesis** of male rats, qualitative and quantitative.^[177]

Follow up of previous research: whole plant ethanolic extract had positive effect in male rats **reproductive system**: testis volume, blood vessels and spermatogenesis.^[178]

Leaves ethanolic extract had positive effects on male rats **reproductive system**, morphology and spermatogenesis.^[179]

	<p>Whole plant powder was supplemented (250 mg/kg/day by gavage for 8 weeks) to treat Varicocele (induced by partial occluding of the left kidney vein). Positive effects were observed in sexual organs physical health, sex hormones, spermatogenesis and oxidant-antioxidant biochemicals.^[180]</p> <p>Aerial parts 80% aqueous ethanolic extract was analyzed for TPC. It was used to prepare a cream (4%) for treatment of eczema, showing significant amelioration.^[181]</p> <p>Whole plant was defatted with PE and extracted with methanol, and the resulting extract was analyzed for TFC and TPC. It was used to prepare a formulation, in combination with extract of <i>Glycyrrhiza globra</i> showing significant stability and pH.^[182]</p> <p>Long term use of aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract proved toxic to rats, where toxicity was verified by several biomarkers. This includes lower concentrations than higher ones that were confirmed toxic in previous studies, that stated that this extract is safe.^[183]</p> <p>HPLC analysis of aerial parts of cultivated plants yielded 15 alkaloids that were tested for acute toxicity and wound healing, both <i>in vitro</i>. Eight of these alkaloids had wound healing activity and the most active was Sanguinarine. The isolated alkaloids that were previously mentioned are: Hydrastine, Bicuculline, Protopine, Coptisine, Dihydrosanguinarine, Fumaramidine, Sanguinarine, Fumaramine, Dihydrofumariline, 8-Oxocoptisine and Norjuziphine. In addition, N-methylstylophine, Noroxyhydrastinine, Lahorine and Microcarpine were also isolated (Figure 9C).^[184]</p>
<i>F. petteri</i>	<p>Forty Isoquinoline alkaloids were isolated from fourteen <i>Fumaria</i> species where ten of them are native to the RR, including this species (see <i>F. asepala</i>). These alkaloids were tested for antimicrobial and antiviral activities showing moderate to high potency.^[50]</p> <p>Whole plant methanol-chloroform (1:1) extract was had significant enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE) activity.^[54]</p> <p>Aerial parts ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was analyzed with GC-MS yielding eight previously known alkaloids (% of total alkaloid content): Dihydrofumariline 7 (Figure 10), in addition to Sinactine 10, Protopine 37, Cryptopine 5, Parfumine 7, Fumariline 20, Fumarophycine 13 and Dihydrosanguinarine 2.^[72]</p>

*Unless stated otherwise, percentages of solvent mixtures are V/V.

Figure 2: Natural products isolated from *F. asepala*.

Figure 3: Natural products isolated from *F. bracteosa*.

Figure 4A: Natural products isolated from *F. capreolata*.

Figure 4B: Natural products isolated from *F. capreolata*.

Figure 5A: Natural products isolated from *F. densiflora*.

Figure 5B: Natural products isolated from *F. densiflora*.

Figure 6: Natural products isolated from *F. gaillardotii*.

Figure 7: Natural products isolated from *F. kralikii*.

Figure 8: Natural products isolated from *F. officinalis*.

Figure 9A: Natural products isolated from *F. parviflora*.

Figure 9B: Natural products isolated from *F. parviflora*.

Figure 9C: Natural products isolated from *F. parviflora*.

Dihydrofumariline

Ref. 72

Figure 10: Natural products isolated from *F. petteri*.

5. DISCUSSION

Reviewing *Fumaria* plants of Israel and Palestine was a challenging yet very interesting task, mainly due to the presence and great diversity of alkaloids in these species. Most of these alkaloids are present in all species with obvious differences in their concentrations. Because of this fact, it is emphasized in many articles that some compounds were isolated from certain species for the first time, indicating that these compounds were previously known. One of the best examples of these articles was published by J. Sousek *et al.*^[185] This work was published in 1999, and it does not report previously unknown natural products. Authors analyzed the alkaloid and organic acids content of eight *Fumaria* species, four of them native to the RR: *F. capreolata*, *F. densiflora*, *F. officinalis* and *F. parviflora*. The analysis aimed to qualitatively and quantitatively detect the presence of Isoquinoline alkaloids Adlumiceine (**Figure 11**), Adlumidiceine, Coptisine, Corytuberine, Cryptopine, Fumaricine, Fumariline, Fumaritine, Fumarophycine, *O*-methylfumarophycine, Palmatine, Parfumine, Protopine, Sinactine, Stylophine, and *N*-methylstylophine. A detailed table (table 1 in the cited article) is provided that includes even the dates of harvesting the plants. In a second table (table 2 in the cited article), alkaloids isolated for the first time from each species are presented. This presentation is very highly helpful.

Figure 11: Structure of Adlumiceine (methyl ester).

The published reports about *Fumaria densiflora* include contradicting presentations. B. Şener published in 1984 the structure of Densiflorine that she isolated as a new compound from this species, and its structure is presented in **Figure 5A**.^[78] This structure is identical to that presented in many chemical databases such as PubChem (PubChem CID 343060).^[186] But a year earlier (1983), M.E. Popova *ahc* reported the isolation of the same compound as a new natural product and presented a notably different structure.^[187] And to increase the confusion, the same compound is presented in PubChem with a different PubChem CID (177184)^[188], which is identical to the structure presented by M.E. Popova *ahc*. Both structures are shown in **Figure 12**.

Figure 12: Two different reported structures of Densiflorine.

In a recent work, A.H. Roni *ahc* performed molecular docking of several compounds as antiviral agents, including Densiflorine, and the presented a structure like that presented by M.E. Popova *ahc*.^[189]

Following the mentioned above contradictory concerning the structure of Densiflorine, it is important to highlight analytical efforts that add more information about natural products, their structures and their isolation. In the work of M.H. Abu Zarga *et al.* that reported the isolation and characterization of Fumadensine (**Figure 5A**) as a new compound from *Fumaria densiflora*^[80], they included its decomposition with Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA). This was done as additional way of confirming its structure. See **Figure 13**.

Figure 13: Decomposition of Fumadensine with TFA (Ref. 80).

T. Fafal and M.A. Önrür published an outstanding article in 2007 about Determination of protopine in *F. densiflora* by TLC-densitometric and spectrophotometric method.^[190] In addition to the efficiency and accuracy of this method, the authors presented all the alkaloids that were isolated from 18 *Fumaria* species. They presented the information in two very clear tables, qualitative and quantitative.

In 1938, R.H. Manske published the alkaloid composition of *Fumaria officinalis*.^[191] He reported (quantitatively) the isolation and characterization of seven alkaloids: Aurotensine, Tetrahydrocoptisine, Cryptocavine (**Figure 14**), Protopine, Sinactine and two new alkaloids that he indicated them with molecular formulas and symbols F36 and F37. The structures of the alkaloids were not presented. However, the structure of Cryptocavine was debated, and in 1955, A.F. Thomas *et al.* (a research group headed by R.H. Manske) resolved the debate and the similarity to the structure of Cryptopine by chemical modifications.^[192]

Figure 14: Alkaloids isolated from *Fumaria officinalis*.

Additional clarity to the structures of alkaloids isolated from *Fumaria officinalis* was presented by C. Seger *et al.* (2004). They published a comprehensive ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR peak assignment of Adlumine, Corlumine, Corydamine, Cryptopine, Fumarophycine, *O*-methylfumarophycine, Hydrastine, Parfumine, Protopine and Sinactine.^[193]

The extraction of *Fumaria officinalis* was thoroughly studied and improved by several research groups. S. Khamtache-Abderahimi *et al.* published the optimization of phenolic compounds extraction, affording higher yields of TFC and TPC, and consequently, the antioxidant capacity measured with ABTS and DPPH methods.^[194] In a recent work, G. Mammadova and P. Koseoglu-Yilmaz improved the extraction (HPLC) of Fumaric acid.^[195] R. Ashowen Ahmoda *et al.* investigated the effect of heating on the yields of extraction and optimized this method for polyphenols and flavonoids in *F. officinalis*.^[196]

Of all *Fumaria* species of the RR, *Fumaria parviflora* is the most studied and published (Table 3). But one of the “strangest” articles about this plant was published by A. Bhargava *et al.*^[197] They analyzed whole plant methanolic extract by special method of HPLC yielding 42 compounds arranged in four tables. Strangely enough, under the column title of “assigned substance”, all 42 entries are “unknown”.

Fumaria parviflora is considered a medicinal plant in most parts of its natural habitat. But in some cases, it becomes hazardous weed, and some studies were published about its control. One of these articles was published by B. Hajjaj *et al.*, where they investigated the control of this plant that infest wheat crop, by two synthetic herbicides, Florasulam and 2,4-D (2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid).^[198]

M. Tashakorizadeh ahc investigated the effect of copper (ancient copper mine) and drought on growth and essential oil yield and composition.^[199] Drought had major effect on both parameters, suggesting that this plant can not tolerate drought stress, and its phytoremediation was clearly limited. This research was followed up and three additional articles were published by the same research group.^[200,201,202]

In a very recent research, V. Ramezani ahc tested the aerial parts aqueous extract in breastfeeding infants for anti-colic activity in comparison with Simethicone, where the extract had stronger effect.^[172] This achievement is questionable. Simethicone is a polydimethylsiloxane mixed with silicon dioxide (**Figure 15**).^[203]

Figure 15: Structure of Simethicone.

Reference drugs usually have proven activity, and this is not the case of Simethicone. In 1994, T.J. Metcalf ahc published a research that was carried out to “determine the efficacy of simethicone in the treatment of infant colic”^[204] They concluded that “Simethicone is no more effective than placebo”. Moreover, C. Evans and W.P. Lorentz published a research that used a mixture of plants to treat infant colic showing notable ameliorative effect.^[205] They compared their findings to Simethicone and even mentioned that some other synthetic medications are more effective Simethicone.

To conclude this part of the discussion, a summary of published *Fumaria* extract assisted preparations of nanoparticles (NPs) and their activities, is presented in **Table 4**.

Table 4: NPs prepared with *Fumaria* plants (of the RR) and their medicinal activities.

Species	NP	Property-Activity, reference
<i>F. officinalis</i>	Ag	Antibacterial ^[206]
	Fe ₃ O ₄	Absorbing material, antioxidant ^[207]
	Mn	Anticancer ^[208]
	Extract loaded on Chitosan	Wound healing ^[209]
	Ni	Anticancer ^[210]
	Zn	Antileukemia ^[211]

	ZnO	Antibacterial, antioxidant ^[212]
<i>F. parviflora</i>	Ag	Antibacterial, antioxidant ^[213]
	Ag	Anticancer ^[214]
	Ag	Antibacterial ^[215]
	Extract coated with Maltodextrin and/or gum Arabic	Antioxidant ^[216]
	Extract loaded on Chitosan	Antiparasitic ^[217]
	ZnO	Antibacterial, antioxidant ^[218]

6. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) *Fumaria* plants of Israel and Palestine were partially investigated and published.
- 2) A research effort is needed to achieve the completion of this research.
- 3) *Fumaria* plants of Israel and Palestine contain an amazing diversity of alkaloids.
- 4) These alkaloids must be tested for drug development.
- 5) It is vitally important to share species data among scholars in the RR.

7. REFERENCES

1. Peng, H-W., Xiang, K-L., Lian, L., Liu, B., Erst, A.S., Gao, T-G., Ortiz, R., Jabbour, F., Chen, Z-D., Wang, W., A revised tribal classification of Papaveraceae (poppy family) based on molecular and morphological data. *Taxon.*, 2024; 73: 762-783. DOI: 10.1002/tax.13175
2. Gupta, P.C., Sharma, N., Rao, C.V., A review on ethnobotany, phytochemistry and pharmacology of *Fumaria indica* (Fumitory). *Asian Pac. J. Trop. Biomed.*, 2012; 2: 665-669. DOI: 10.1016/S2221-1691(12)60117-8
3. Flora of Israel and Adjacent Areas: *Fumaria*
4. Florapal: Flora Palaestina Ethnobotany
5. Sallon, S., Myers, D., Jamous, R., Paavilineen, H., Fragman-Sapir, O., Abuzaitoun, S.Y., Eisner, D., Solowey, E. and Ali-Shtayeh, M.S., Florapal an ethnobotanical website of Flora Palaestina reflects changing patterns of plant use in this region during the mid-20th to 21st century. *Ethnobot. Res. Appl.*, 2025; 31: 1-19. DOI: 10.32859/era.31.34.1-19
6. Ali-Shtayeh, M.S., Jamous, R.M., Zaitoun, S.Y., Qasem, I.B., In-vitro screening of acetylcholinesterase inhibitory activity of extracts from Palestinian indigenous flora in relation to the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. *Funct. Foods Health Dis.*, 2014; 4: 381-400. DOI: 10.31989/ffhd.v4i9.149

7. Rajagopal, P.L., Jasmin, R., Sreejith, K.R., Premaletha, K., Aneeshia, S., *Fumaria* species-An elaborative pharmacological review. *Br. J. Med. Health Res.*, 2018; 7: 22-41. DOI: 10.46624/bjmhr.2020.v7.i1.002
8. Zhang, R., Guo, Q., Kennelly, E.J., Long, C., Chai, X., Diverse alkaloids and biological activities of *Fumaria* (Papaveraceae): An ethnomedicinal group. *Fitoterapia.*, 2020; 146: 104697. DOI: 10.1016/j.fitote.2020.104697
9. Kiumarsi F., Derakhshan A.R. Gastrointestinal and Hepatic Effects of *Fumaria* Species in Traditional Persian Medicine and Modern Medical Studies: A Narrative Review. *J. Sabzevar Univ. Med. Sci.*, 2022; 29: 697-718. [[Journal Website](#), article in Persian]
10. Goetz, P., Ghedira, K., Le Jeune, R., *Fumaria officinalis* L. (Fumariaceae). *Phytotherapie.*, 2009; 7: 221–225. DOI: 10.1007/s10298-009-0399-2 [Article in French]
11. Sajjad, S., Babaeimarzangou, S. S., Aghajanshakeri, S.H., Anousheh, D., Mikaili, P., Ethno-botanical, bioactivities and medicinal mysteries of *Fumaria officinalis* (common fumitory). *J. Pharm. Biomed. Sci.*, 2015; 5: 857-862. [[ResearchGate](#)]
12. Dutta, R., Sharma, M.K., Jha, M., A review on ethnobotanical, phytochemistry, bioactivities and medicinal mysteries of *Fumaria officinalis* (Common Fumitory). *EAS J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 2019; 1: 99-105. DOI: 10.36349/easjpp.2019.v01i04.004
13. Al-Snafi, A.E., Constituents and pharmacology of *Fumaria officinalis* - A review. *IOSR J. Pharm.*, 2020; 10: 17-25. [[ResearchGate](#)]
14. Aguiar, R., *Fumaria officinalis* L. active compounds and biological activities: A review. *Int. J. Herb. Med.*, 2023; 11: 144-151. DOI: 10.22271/flora.2023.v11.i5b.900
15. Prokopenko, Y., Surzhykov, I., Golovchenko, O., Mishchenko, V., Georgiyants, V., *Fumaria officinalis*: Phytochemical complexity and its medicinal significance. *Fitoterapia.* 2025; 186: 106780. DOI: 10.1016/j.fitote.2025.106780
16. Kumar, S., Sharma, A.K., Kamboj, A., *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. (Fumitory): A traditional herbal medicine with modern evidence. *Asian J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 2017; 3: 200-207. [[Journal Website](#)]
17. Al-Snafi, A.E., *Fumaria parviflora* - A Review. *Indo Am. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2018; 5: 1728-1738. [[ResearchGate](#)]
18. Tayade, P.K., Mangala Jadhav, M., Medicinal Uses and Pharmacological Activities of Parpatak (*Fumaria parviflora* Lam.) - A Review. *World J. Pharm. Res.*, 2019; 8: 337-344. DOI: 10.20959/wjpr20196-14793

19. Jamaldeen, F.N., Sofi, G., Fahim, M.F., Aleem, M., Begum, E.M., Shahatra (*F. parviflora* Lam) - a comprehensive review of its ethnopharmacology, phytochemistry and pharmacology. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 2022; 286: 114839. DOI: 10.1016/j.jep.2021.114839
20. Kumar, N., Devi, R., Pratibha, P., Kumar, S., Saurav, S., Singh Pathania, M., Anita Kumari, A., A Review on Cytomorphological, Medicinal, Phytochemical and Pharmacological Potential of Common Weed of Wheat Crop of Himachal Pradesh: *Fumaria Parviflora*. *Plant Health Arch.*, 2024; 2: 26-30. DOI: 10.54083/PHA/2.1.2024/26-30
21. Sharma, A., Yadav, P., Jangra, R., Singh, S., Kumar, V., Badhwar, P., Gopalan, N., Gill, S.S., Gill, R., From roots to remedies: Exploration of medicinal potential of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. in drug discovery. *Pharmacol. Res. Nat. Prod.*, 2025; 100319. DOI: 10.1016/j.prenap.2025.100319
22. Rajaei, P., Mohamadi, N., Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants of Hezar mountain allocated in South East of Iran. *Iran. J. Pharm. Res.*, 2012; 11: 1153-1167. [ResearchGate]
23. Ahvazi, M., Khalighi-Sigaroodi, F., Charkhchiyan, M.M., Mojab, F., Mozaffarian, V.A., Zakeri, H., Introduction of medicinal plants species with the most traditional usage in Alamut region. *Iran. J. Pharm. Res.*, 2012; 11: 185-194. [ResearchGate]
24. Naghibi, F., Esmaeili, S., Malekmohammadi, M., Hassanpour, A., Mosaddegh, M., Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants used traditionally in two villages of Hamedan, Iran. *Res. J. Pharmacog.*, 2014; 1: 7-14. [Journal Website]
25. Ahmadipour, S., Mohsenzadeh, A., Eftekhari, Z., Ahmadipour, S., An overview of the most important medicinal plants affecting on child's jaundice in ethnobotanical resource of Iran. *Der Pharm. Lett.*, 2016; 8: 135-139. [ResearchGate]
26. Baharvand-Ahmadi, B., Asadi-Samani, M., Medicinal plants and treatment of hypertension; evidence from Iran. *J. Nephroarmacol.*, 2017; 6: 3-8. [Journal Website]
27. Keshavarzi, M., Mosaferi, S., An ethnobotanical survey on some areas of northwest of Isfahan province, Iran. *Collect. Bot.*, 2019; 38: 10-3989. DOI: 10.3989/collectbot.2019.v38.008
28. Ebadi, M., Eftekharian, R., Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants used in Ahar-Arasbaran (protected area in East Azerbaijan Province of Iran). *Mediterr. Botany.*, 2019; 40: 209-214. DOI: 10.5209/mbot.62985

29. Moghanloo, L., Ghahremani Nezhad, F., Vafadar, M., Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants in the central district of the Zanjan county, Zanjan province, Iran. *J. Herb. Drugs.*, 2019; 9: 121-131. [[ResearchGate](#)]
30. Buso, P., Manfredini, S., Ahmadi-Ashtiani, H.R., Sciabica, S., Buzzi, R., Vertuani, S., Baldisserotto, A., Iranian Medicinal Plants: From Ethnomedicine to Actual Studies. *Medicina.*, 2020; 56: 97. DOI: 10.3390/medicina56030097
31. Mangena, P., Dalvadi, H., Bahmani, M., Medicinal plants and treatment of itching: the most important native medicinal plants of Iran used in itching based on ethnobotanical documents. *Plant Biotechnol. Persa.*, 2021; 3: 32-37. [[Journal Website](#)]
32. Ari, S., Temel, M., Kargioğlu, M., Konuk, M., Ethnobotanical survey of plants used in Afyonkarahisar -Turkey. *J. Ethnobiol. Ethnomed.*, 2015; 11: 84. DOI: 10.1186/s13002-015-0067-6
33. Hachemi, N., Hasnaoui, O., Bouazza, M., Benmehdi, I., Medjati, N., The therophytes aromatic and medicinal plants of the southern slopes of the mountains of Tlemcen (western Algeria) between utility and degradation. *Res. J. Pharm. Biol. Chem. Sci.*, 2013; 4: 1194-1203. [[ResearchGate](#)]
34. Sofiane, I., Seridi, R., Ethnomedicine exploration of medicinal plants: *Fumaria capreolata* L. and *Calendula suffruticosa* Vahl in Numidia (north-eastern Algeria). *Biodiv. Res. Conserv.*, 2023; 70: 19-32. DOI 10.14746/biorc.2023.70.3
35. Guarino, C., De Simone, L., Santoro, S., Ethnobotanical study of the Sannio area, Campania, southern Italy. *Ethnobot. Res. Appl.*, 2008; 6: 255-317. DOI: 10.17348/era.6.0.255-317
36. Güzel, Y., Güzelşemme, M., Miski, M., Ethnobotany of medicinal plants used in Antakya: A multicultural district in Hatay Province of Turkey. *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 2015; 174: 118-152. DOI: 10.1016/j.jep.2015.07.042
37. Al-Traboulsi, M., Alaib, M.A., A survey of medicinal plants of Wadi Al-Kouf in Al-Jabal Al-Akhdar, Libya. *Nat. Croat.*, 2021; 30: 389-404. DOI: 10.20302/NC.2021.30.25
38. Valiakos, E., Marselos, M., Sakellaridis, N., Constantinidis, T., Skaltsa, H., Ethnopharmacological approach to the herbal medicines of the "Antidotes" in Nikolaos Myrepsos' *Dynameron*. *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 2015; 163: 68-82. DOI: 10.1016/j.jep.2015.01.005
39. Chaachouay, N., Benkhnigue, O., Fadli, M., El Ibaoui, H., Zidane, L., Ethnobotanical and ethnopharmacological studies of medicinal and aromatic plants used in the treatment of

- metabolic diseases in the Moroccan Rif. *Heliyon.*, 2019; 5: e02191. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02191
40. Idm'hand, E., Msanda, F., Cherifi, K., Ethnopharmacological review of medicinal plants used to manage diabetes in Morocco. *Clin. Phytosci.*, 2020; 6: 18. DOI: 10.1186/s40816-020-00166-z
41. Eddouks, M., Maghrani, M., Lemhadri, A., Ouahidi, M.L., Jouad, H., Ethnopharmacological survey of medicinal plants used for the treatment of diabetes mellitus, hypertension and cardiac diseases in the south-east region of Morocco (Tafilalet). *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 2002; 82: 97-103. DOI: 10.1016/s0378-8741(02)00164-2
42. Aziz, M.A., Adnan, M., Khan, A.H., Shahat, A.A., Al-Said, M.S., Ullah, R., Traditional uses of medicinal plants practiced by the indigenous communities at Mohmand Agency, FATA, Pakistan. *J. Ethnobiol. Ethnomed.*, 2018; 14: 2. doi: 10.1186/s13002-017-0204-5
43. Kandpal, A.S., Kumar, S., Kandpal, N.K., Diversity of Ethno-medicinal Plant: A Study in Pithoragarh District of Uttarakhand. *Agric. Rev.*, 2023; 44: 568-572. DOI: 10.18805/ag.R-2271
44. Sohrabi-Akbarabadi, T., Khosravi, A.R., Ethnobotanical Study of Medicinal Plants Around Akbarabad Village in Kavar District, Fars Province, Iran. *Res. Rev. J. Bot. Sci.* 2022; 11: JBS-22-59620. DOI: 10.4172/2320-0189.11.6.012
45. Jahantab, E., Hosseini, S.H., Sadeghi, Z., Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants, Fasa County, Iran. *J. Med. Plants.*, 2023; 22: 88-112. DOI: 10.61186/jmp.22.86.88
46. Sherwani, N., Al-Dhafri, K.S., Farooq, S.A., An ethnobotanical study of indigenous medicinal plants of Oman. *Asian J. Sci. Res.*, 2021; 14: 43-56. DOI: 10.3923/ajsr.2021.43.56
47. Sancar, P.Y., Taskin, I.I., In vitro cytotoxic effects of some *Fumaria* L. (Papaveraceae) species methanolic extracts on cancer cell lines. *Turk. J. Nat. Sci.*, 2024; 13: 25-29. DOI: 10.46810/tdfd.1287018
48. Tosun, A., Bahadir, Ö., Altanlar, N., Antimicrobial activity of some plants used in folk medicine in Turkey. *Turk. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2006; 3: 167-76. [ResearchGate]
49. Jafari-Sales, A., Mobaiyen, H., Jafari, B., Sayyahi, J., Assessment of Antibacterial Effect of Alcoholic Extract of *Centaurea depressa* M.B., *Reseda lutea* L. and *Fumaria asepala* on Selected Standard Strains in Vitro. *Sci. J. Nurs. Midwif. Paramed. Facul.*, 2019; 5: 63-73. [ResearchGate, article in Persian]

50. Orhan, I., Ozçelik, B., Karaoğlu, T., Sener, B., Antiviral and antimicrobial profiles of selected Isoquinoline alkaloids from *Fumaria* and *Corydalis* species. *Z. Naturforsch. Biosci.*, 2007; 62: 19-26. DOI: 10.1515/znc-2007-1-204
51. Mohseni, M., Azimi, A.A., Hashemloian, B.D., Farzamisepehr, M., Phytochemical investigation of alkaloid fractions of *Fumaria vaillantii* and *F. asepala* and their antifungal influence on gene expression pattern in *Aspergillus* species. *Turk. J. Bot.*, 2023; 47: 244-255. DOI: 10.55730/1300-008X.2762
52. Önder, A., Çınar, A.S., Gençaslan, G., Çoban, T., Antioxidant potentials of the extracts from 14 selected medicinal plants. *J. Med. Herbs Ethnomed.*, 2020; 6: 17-20. DOI: 10.25081/jmhe.2020.v6.6060
53. Sener, B., Turkish Species of *Fumaria* and their alkaloids, V. Alkaloids from *Fumaria capreolata* and *Fumaria asepala*. *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1985; 48: 670. DOI: 10.1021/np50040a034
54. Orhan, I., Sener, B., Choudhary, M.I., Khalid, A., Acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase inhibitory activity of some Turkish medicinal plants. *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 2004; 91: 57-60. DOI: 10.1016/j.jep.2003.11.016
55. Uras, I.S., Kursat, M., Konuklugil, B., Şenturk, M., Effects of Some Turkish Plant Extracts on Carbonic Anhydrase and Cholinesterase Enzymes. *Stud. Univ. Babeş-Bolyai Chem.*, 2024; 69: 115-127. DOI:10.24193/subbchem.2024.4.08
56. Sancar, P.Y., Analysis of the Essential Oil Composition, Antimicrobial Activity and Antioxidant Capacity of *Fumaria asepala* Boiss. and *Fumaria schleicheri* Soy. Will. subsp. *microcarpa* Hausskn. from Turkey. *Int. J. Pure Appl. Sci.*, 2023; 9: 29-37. DOI: 10.29132/ijpas.1089824
57. Fazly Bazzaz, B.S., Haririzadeh, G., Screening of Iranian Plants for Antimicrobial Activity, *Pharm. Biol.*, 2003; 41(8): 573-583, DOI: 10.1080/13880200390501488
58. Halim, A.F., Salama, O.M. and Amer, M.M., Alkaloids of *Fumaria bracteosa*. *Planta Med.*, 1986; 52: 414. DOI: 10.1055/s-2007-969209
59. Bribi, N., Belmouhoub, M., Maiza, F., Anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities of ethanolic extract of *Fumaria capreolata*. *Phytothérapie.*, 2017; 15: 211-216. DOI: 10.1007/s10298-016-1035-6
60. Bribi, N., Algieri, F., Rodriguez-Nogales, A., Vezza, T., Garrido-Mesa, J., Utrilla, M.P., Contreras, M., Maiza, F., Segura-Carretero, A., Rodriguez-Cabezas, M.E., Gálvez, J., Intestinal anti-inflammatory effects of total alkaloid extract from *Fumaria capreolata* in

- the DNBS model of mice colitis and intestinal epithelial CMT93 cells. *Phytomedicine*, 2016; 23: 901-913. DOI: 10.1016/j.phymed.2016.05.003
61. Bribi, N., Rodríguez-Nogales, A., Vezza, T., Algieri, F., Rodriguez-Cabezas, M.E., Garrido-Mesa, J., Gálvez, J., Intestinal anti-inflammatory activity of the total alkaloid fraction from *Fumaria capreolata* in the DSS model of colitis in mice, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2020; 30: 127414. DOI: 10.1016/j.bmcl.2020.127414
62. Bribi, N., Algieri, F., Rodríguez-Nogales, A., Garrido-Mesa, J., Vezza, T., Maiza, F., Utrilla, M.P., Rodriguez-Cabezas, M.E., Galvez, J., Antinociceptive and Anti-Inflammatory Effects of Total Alkaloid Extract from *Fumaria capreolata*. *Evid. Based Complement. Alternat. Med.*, 2015; 736895. DOI: 10.1155/2015/73689563)
63. Mezhoud, K., Benmokhtar, M., Smati, D., Contribution à l'étude de *Fumaria cepreolata* L. (Papaveraceae), Wilaya de Constantine: caractérisation phytochimique et recherche de l'activité anti-inflammatoire. *Batna J. Med. Sci.*, 2018; 5: 26-28. DOI: 10.48087/BJMSoa.2018.5107 [Article in French]
64. Maiza-Benabdesselam, F., Khentache, S., Bougoffa, K., Chibane, M., Adach, S., Chapeleur, Y., Henry, M., Laurain-Mattar, D., Antioxidant activities of alkaloid extracts of two Algerian species of *Fumaria*: *Fumaria capreolata* and *Fumaria bastardii*. *Rec. Nat. Prod.*, 2007; 1: 28-35. [ResearchGate]
65. Jin, D.P., Cao, S.Q., Cheng, F., Xue, Z.S., Li, R.Z., Pu, Y.L., Zhu, D.Y., Bao, W., Xu, X.T., Wang, S.H., A Gold (I)-Catalyzed Cyclization/Semipinacol Rearrangement Cascade of 1, 6-Enynes to Access Spiro [4.5] decanes and 7-Azaspiro [4.5] decanes. *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2023; 365: 312-317. DOI: 10.1002/adsc.202201266
66. Sofiane, I., Seridi, R., Phytochemical profile, total phenolic content and antioxidant activity of ethanolic extract of fumitory (*Fumaria capreolata* L.) from Algeria. *Eur. J. Biol. Res.*, 2021; 11: 404-416. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5484499
67. Bribi, N., Bouguezza, Y., Maiza-Benabdesselam, F., Evaluation of erythrocytes toxicity and antioxidant activity of alkaloids of *Fumaria capreolata*. *Int. J. Pharm. Bio Sci.*, 2013; 4: 770-776. [ResearchGate]
68. Bribi, N., Merakeb, M.S., Afenai, S., Effect of *Fumaria Capreolata* Total Alkaloid Extract on Acetic Acid-induced Ulcerative Colitis in NMRI Mice. *Int. J. Adv. Res. MicroBiol. Immunol.*, 2025; 8: 1-6. [ResearchGate]
69. Tanahashi, T., Zenk, M.H., Isoquinoline alkaloids from cell suspension cultures of *Fumaria capreolata*. *Plant Cell Rep.*, 1985; 4: 96-99. DOI: 10.1007/BF00269216

70. Şener, B., Turkish Species of *Fumaria* L. and Their Alkaloids VI. Alkaloids of *Fumaria capreolata* L. *Int. J. Crude Drug Res.*, 1985; 23: 161–163. DOI: 10.3109/13880208509069024
71. Forgacs, P., Provost, J., Touche, A., Jehanno, A., Alkaloids from *Fumaria capreolata* and *Fumaria bella*. *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1986; 49: 178-179. DOI: 10.1021/np50043a036
72. Suau, R., Cabezudo, B., Rico, R., Nájera, F., López-Romero, J.M., Direct determination of alkaloid contents in *Fumaria* species by GC-MS. *Phytochem. Anal.*, 2002; 13: 363-367. DOI: 10.1002/pca.669
73. Maiza-Benabdesselam, F., Chibane, M., Madani, K., Max, H., Adach, S., Determination of Isoquinoline alkaloids contents in two Algerian species of *Fumaria* (*Fumaria capreolata* and *Fumaria bastardi*). *Afr. J. Biotechnol.*, 2007; 6: 2487-2492. DOI: 10.5897/AJB2007.000-2394
74. Contreras, M.D., Bribe, N., Gómez-Caravaca, A.M., Gálvez, J., Segura-Carretero, A., Alkaloids Profiling of *Fumaria capreolata* by Analytical Platforms Based on the Hyphenation of Gas Chromatography and Liquid Chromatography with Quadrupole-Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry. *Int. J. Anal. Chem.*, 2017; 5178729. DOI: 10.1155/2017/5178729
75. Păltinean, R., Mocan, A., Vlase, L., Gheldiu, A.M., Crişan, G., Ielciu, I., Voştinaru, O., Crişan, O., Evaluation of Polyphenolic Content, Antioxidant and Diuretic Activities of Six *Fumaria* Species. *Molecules.*, 2017; 22: 639. DOI: 10.3390/molecules22040639
76. Çelik, T.A., Aslantürk, Ö.S., Yılmaz, E.Ş., Güzel, Y., Antioxidant and Cytotoxic Activities of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. and *Fumaria capreolata* L. *KSU J. Agric. Nat.*, 2022; 25: 819-827. DOI: 10.18016/ksutarimdoga.vi.899937
77. Al-Ghazzawi, A.M., Abu Zarga, M.H., Abdalla, S.S., Chemical constituents of *Fumaria densiflora* and the effects of some isolated spirobenzylisoquinoline alkaloids on murine isolated ileum and perfused heart. *Nat. Prod. Res.*, 2020; 34: 1180-1185. DOI: 10.1080/14786419.2018.1550761
78. Şener, B., Densiflorine, a New Alkaloid from *Fumaria densiflora* DC. *Int. J. Crude Drug Res.*, 1984; 22: 79–80. DOI: 10.3109/13880208409070656
79. Aboudi, A.F., Al-Eisawi, D.M., Sabri, S.S., Abu Zarga, M.H., Alkaloids of *Fumaria densiflora*. *J. Nat. Prod.* 1986; 49: 370. DOI: 10.1021/np50044a046
80. Abu Zarga, M.H., Sabri, S.S., Firdous, S., Shamma, M., Fumadensine, a phthalideisoquinoline from *Fumaria densiflora*. *Phytochemistry.*, 1987; 26: 233-1234. DOI: 10.1016/S0031-9422(00)82396-1

81. Táborská, E., Bochořáková, H., Soušek, J., Sedmera, P., Vavrečková, C., Šimánek, V., *Fumaria densiflora* DC. Alkaloids. *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.* 1996; *61*: 1064-1072. DOI: 10.1135/cccc19961064
82. Táborská, E., Bochorakova, H., Sousek, J., Sedmera, P., Havlíček, V., Šimánek, V., Fumaflorine, a New 1-Benzylisoquinoline Alkaloid from *Fumaria densiflora*. *Chem. Inform.*, 1997; *28*. DOI: 10.1002/CHIN.199741267. Originally published in *Heterocycles*, 1997; *45*: 817-821.
83. Orhan, I.E., Şener, B., Musharraf, S.G., Antioxidant and hepatoprotective activity appraisal of four selected *Fumaria* species and their total phenol and flavonoid quantities. *Exp. Toxicol. Pathol.*, 2012; *64*: 205-209. DOI: 10.1016/j.etp.2010.08.007
84. Orhan, I.E., Ozturk, N., Sener, B., Antiprotozoal assessment and phenolic acid profiling of five *Fumaria* (fumitory) species. *Asian Pac. J. Trop. Med.*, 2015; *8*: 283-286. DOI: 10.1016/S1995-7645(14)60331-X
85. Erdoğan, T.F., Brine shrimp lethality bioassay of *Fumaria densiflora* Dc. and *Fumaria officinalis* L. extracts. *Hacettepe Univ. J. Facul. Pharm.*, 2009; *2*: 125-132. [Journal Website]
86. Soušek, J., Vavreckova, C., Psotova, J., Ulrichova, J., Šimánek, V., November. Antioxidant and antilipoperoxidant activities of alkaloid and phenolic extracts of eight *Fumaria* species. *Acta Hort.*, 1999; *501*: 239-244. DOI: 10.17660/ActaHortic.1999.501.38
87. Şener, B., Turkish Species of *Fumaria* L. and Their Alkaloids II. Alkaloids of *Fumaria Gaillardotii* Boiss. *Int. J. Crude Drug Res.*, 1983; *21*: 135-139. DOI: 10.3109/13880208309070626
88. Abou-Donia, A.H., EI-Masry, S., Saleh, M.R., Phillipson, J.D., Alkaloids from *Fumaria judaica*. *Planta Med.*, 1980; *40*: 295-298. DOI: 10.1055/s-2008-1074972
89. Şener, B., Turkish Species of *Fumaria* L. and Their Alkaloids III. Alkaloids of *Fumaria judaica* Boiss. *Int. J. Crude Drug Res.*, 1984; *22*: 181-183. DOI: 10.3109/13880208409070673
90. Colton, M.D., Guinaudeau, H., Shamma, M., Önür, M.A., Gözler, T., (-)-Norfumaritine: A New Spirobenzylisoquinoline Alkaloid from *Fumaria kralikii*. *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1985; *48*: 846-847. DOI: 10.1021/np50041a030
91. Doncheva, T., Yordanova, G., Vutov, V., Kostova, N., Philipov, S., Comparative Study of Alkaloid Pattern of Four Bulgarian *Fumaria* Species. *Nat. Prod. Commun.* 2016; *11*: 211-212. DOI: 10.1177/1934578X1601100220

92. Ivanov, I., Vrancheva, R., Marchev, A., Petkova, N., Aneva, I., Denev, P., Georgiev, V., Pavlov, A., Antioxidant activities and phenolic compounds in Bulgarian *Fumaria* species. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. Appl. Sci.*, 2014; 3: 296-306. [ResearchGate]
93. Vrancheva, R.Z., Ivanov, I.G., Aneva, I.Y., Dincheva, I.N., Badjakov, I.K., Pavlov, A.I., GC-MS based metabolite profiling of five Bulgarian *Fumaria* species. *J. BioSci. Biotechnol.*, 2014; 3: 195-201. DOI: 10.69085/jbb20143195
94. Şener, B., Turkish Species of *Fumaria* L. and Their Alkaloids IV. Alkaloids of *Fumaria macrocarpa* Parlatores. *Int. J. Crude Drug Res.*, 1984; 22: 185–187. DOI: 10.3109/13880208409070675
95. Loukis, A., Philianos, S., Alkaloids From *Fumaria macrocarpa*. *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1984; 47: 187. DOI: 10.1021/np50031a035
96. Dutta, R., Sharma, M.K., Jha, M., Pharmacological evaluation of antiasthmatic activity of *Fumaria officinalis* extracts. *Plant Arch.* 2020; 20: 4308-4315. [Journal Website]
97. Harabi, M., Tlili, H., Gatran, R., Ben Arfa, A., Neffati, M., Najjaa, H., Phytochemical composition and in vitro biological activities of *Fumaria officinalis* leaves collected from a Tunisian arid region. *Euro-Mediterr. J. Environ. Integr.*, 2025; 10: 1945-1960. DOI: 10.1007/s41207-024-00689-8
98. Shabbir, R., Zaidi, A.A., Shehryaar, Z.A., Farooq, U., Shalabi, E., Quddoos, A., Khan, M.W., Zahra, H., Pasha, A.Z., Anti-hyperlipidemic effect of *Fumaria officinalis* in high-fat-diet induced hyperlipidemic rats. *Tob. Regul. Sci.*, 2023; 9: 3618-3629. DOI: 10.18001/TRS.9.1.253
99. Raafat, K.M., El-Zahaby, S.A., Niosomes of active *Fumaria officinalis* phytochemicals: antidiabetic, antineuropathic, anti-inflammatory, and possible mechanisms of action. *Chin. Med.*, 2020; 15: 40. DOI: 10.1186/s13020-020-00321-1
100. Fatima, S., Akhtar, M.F., Ashraf, K.M., Sharif, A., Saleem, A., Akhtar, B., Peerzada, S., Shabbir, M., Ali, S., Ashraf, W., Antioxidant and alpha amylase inhibitory activities of *Fumaria officinalis* and its antidiabetic potential against alloxan induced diabetes. *Cell. Molec. Biol.* 2019; 65: 50-57. DOI: 10.14715/cmb/2019.65.2.8
101. Yahiaoui, S., Khamtache-Abderrahim, S., Kati, D.E., Bettache, N., Bachir-Bey, M., Anti-inflammatory potential of Isoquinoline alkaloids from *Fumaria officinalis*: in vitro, in vivo, and in silico evaluation. *J. Comput. Aided Mol. Des.*, 2025; 39: 47. DOI: 10.1007/s10822-025-00628-x
102. Aoiadni, N., Jdidi, H., Feki, A.E., Fetoui, H., Koubaa, F.G., Mitochondrial bioenergetics and redox dysfunction in nephrotoxicity induced by pyrethroid permethrin are

- ameliorated by flavonoid-rich fraction. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res. Int.*, 2022; 29: 63973-63987. DOI: 10.1007/s11356-022-20350-7
103. Erdogru, Ö.T., Antibacterial Activities of Some Plant Extracts Used in Folk Medicine. *Pharm. Biol.* 2002; 40: 269-273. DOI: 10.1076/phbi.40.4.269.8474
104. Stanojević, L., Zvezdanović, J., Danilović, B., Cvetković, D., Stanojević, J., Ilić, D., Cakić, M., The antioxidative and antimicrobial activity of the aqueous earth smoke (*Fumaria officinalis* L.): Extract. *Adv. Technol.*, 2018; 7: 31-40. DOI: 10.5937/SavTeh1802031S
105. Khamtache-Abderrahim, S., Lequart-Pillon, M., Gontier, E., Gaillard, I., Pilard, S., Mathiron, D., Djoudad-Kadji, H., Maiza-Benabdesselam, F., Isoquinoline alkaloid fractions of *Fumaria officinalis*: Characterization and evaluation of their antioxidant and antibacterial activities. *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 2016; 94: 1001-1008. DOI: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2016.09.016
106. Dutta, R., Sharma, M.K., Khan, A., Jha, M., Phytochemical and in vitro antioxidant assay of *Fumaria officinalis* leaf extract. *J. Adv. Sci. Res.*, 2020; 11: 176-182. [Journal Website]
107. Ahmoda, R.A., Pirković, A., Milutinović, V., Dekanski, D., Marinković, A., Jovanović, A.A., Radical Scavenging and Ion-Reducing Capacity of *Fumaria officinalis* Extracts Obtained by Traditional and Assisted Extraction Techniques. *Proceedings.*, 2025; 119: 2. DOI: 10.3390/proceedings2025119002
108. Adham, A.N., Sharef, A.Y., Ahmad, H.O., Abdulla, S.S., Evaluation of the antioxidant and anti-ulcer activities of the ethanolic extract of *Fumaria officinalis*. *S. Afr. J. Bot.* 2022; 151: 816-825. DOI: 10.1016/j.sajb.2022.11.008
109. Khare, R., Upmanyu, N., *In vitro – In vivo* Cellular Reprogramming and Antioxidant potential of Herbal Drug: *Fumaria officinalis*. *Res. J. Pharm. Technol.*, 2019; 12: 5517-5523. DOI: 10.5958/0974-360X.2019.00957.0
110. Wasu, S.J., Muley, B.P., Antioxidant Activity of *Fumaria officinalis* Linn and Its Study on Ethanol Induced Immunosuppression. *Res. J. Pharm. Technol.*, 2009; 2: 405-408. [Journal Website]
111. Sharef, A.Y., Aziz, F.M., Adham, A.N., The protective effect of *Fumaria officinalis* against the testicular toxicity of fluoxetine in rat. *Zanco J. Med. Sci.*, 2020; 24: 117-131. DOI: 10.15218/zjms.2020.015

112. Mukhtar, G.Z., Chrioma, B.A., Zainab, R., Muhmmad, A.I., Ibrahim, Y., Yunusa, I., *Cinnamomun cassia*, *Ficus carica* and *Fumaria officinalis* possesses aphrodisiac activity in male Wister rats. *Ann. Exp. Bio.*, 2015; 3: 14-17. [ResearchGate]
113. Gorbunov, N.P., Molokhova, L.G., Sukhanov, A.A., Preparation and the arrhythmic activity of the total alkaloids of *Fumaria officinalis* L. *Pharm. Chem. J.* 1977; 11: 640-642. DOI: 10.1007/BF00780819
114. Ata, S., Farooq, F., Javed, S., Elemental profile of 24 common medicinal plants of Pakistan and its direct link with traditional uses. *J. Med. Plants Res.* 2011; 5: 6164-6168. DOI: 10.5897/JMPR11.866
115. Paltinean, R., Toiu, A., Wauters, J.N., Frederich, M., Tits, M., Angenot, L., Tamas, M., Crisan, G., Phytochemical analysis of *Fumaria officinalis* L. (Fumariaceae). *Farmacia.* 2016; 64: 409-413. [ResearchGate]
116. Chlebek, J., Novák, Z., Kassemová, D., Šafratová, M., Kostelník, J., Malý, L., Ločárek, M., Opletal, L., Hošťálková, A., Hrabínová, M., Kuneš, J., Novotná, P., Urbanová, M., Nováková, L., Macáková, K., Hulcová, D., Solich, P., Pérez Martín, C., Jun, D., Cahlíková, L., Isoquinoline Alkaloids from *Fumaria officinalis* L. and Their Biological Activities Related to Alzheimer's Disease. *Chem. Biodivers.*, 2016; 13: 91-99. DOI: 10.1002/cbdv.201500033
117. Sharma, U.R., Prakash, T., Roopakarki, V.S., Rao, N.R., Goli, D., Hepatoprotective Activity of *Fumaria officinalis* against CCl₄-induced Liver Damage in Rats. *Pharmacologia.*, 2012; 3: 9-14. DOI: 10.5567/pharmacologia.2012.9.14
118. Ferreira, J.F., Peaden, P., Keiser, J., In vitro trematocidal effects of crude alcoholic extracts of *Artemisia annua*, *A. absinthium*, *Asimina triloba*, and *Fumaria officinalis*: trematocidal plant alcoholic extracts. *Parasitol. Res.*, 2011; 109: 1585-1592. DOI: 10.1007/s00436-011-2418-0
119. Khoshvaghti, A., Zamanzadeh, A., Derakhshanian, S., Safi, S., The effect of *Fumaria officinalis* hydroalcoholic extract on blood urea nitrogen and creatinine in New Zealand rabbits. *Med. Plants Int. J. Phytomed. Rel. Ind.* 2013; 5: 155-158. DOI: 10.5958/j.0975-6892.5.3.024
120. Sharma, U.R., Goli, D., Surendra, V., Bose, A., Evaluation of neuropharmacological activity of *Fumaria officinalis* Linn. by study of muscle relaxants activity on experimental animals. *Int. J. Pharm. Eng.*, 2015; 3: 543-551. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14570.16327

121. Iraj, F., Makhmalzadeh B.S., Abedini, M., Aghaei, A., Siahpoush, A., Effect of herbal cream containing *Fumaria officinalis* and silymarin for treatment of eczema: A randomized double-blind controlled clinical trial. *Avicenna J. Phytomed.*, 2022; 12: 155-162. DOI: 10.22038/AJP.2022.19492
122. Ahmoda, R.A., Pirković, A., Milutinović, V., Milošević, M., Marinković, A., Jovanović, A.A., *Fumaria officinalis* Dust as a Source of Bioactives for Potential Dermal Application: Optimization of Extraction Procedures, Phytochemical Profiling, and Effects Related to Skin Health Benefits. *Plants*. 2025; 14: 352. DOI: 10.3390/plants14030352
123. Yahiaoui, S., Khamtache-Abderrahim, S., Otmani, A., Bachir-Bey, M., Kati, D.E., Lequart-Pillon, M., Gontier, E., Maiza-Benabdesselam, F., Evaluation of Acute and Subacute Toxicity of *Fumaria officinalis* Alkaloids in Mice. *Avicenna J. Med. Biochem.* 2022; 10: 128-134. DOI: 10.34172/ajmb.2022.2383
124. Ataei, A., Gholamalipour Alamdari, E., Avarseji, Z., Rahemi Karizaki, A., Study of allelopathic effect of aqueous extract of various organs of *Fumaria parviflora* on morphological, physiological and biochemical characteristics of *Lolium rigidum*. *Appl. Biol.*, 2022; 34: 94-112. [Google Scholar]
125. Singadi, R., Koli, R., Kagawad, P., Maste, M.M., Multifaceted evaluation of *Fumaria parviflora*: from bioactive isolation to anticancer screening and computational drug design. *Nat. Prod. Res.*, 2025; 1-8. DOI: 10.1080/14786419.2025.2538095
126. Fathiazad, F., Hamedeyazdan, S., Khosropanah, M.K., Khaki, A., Hypoglycemic Activity of *Fumaria parviflora* in Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic Rats. *Adv. Pharm. Bull.* 2013; 3: 207-210. DOI: 10.5681/apb.2013.034
127. Ahmed, O.H., Kadheem, E.J., Noman, S.K., The Antihyperglycemic Effect of N-butanol Leaves Extracts of Iraqi *Fumaria parviflora* on Alloxan-prompt Diabetic Rats. *Syst. Rev. Pharm.*, 2020; 11: 757-761. [ResearchGate]
128. Karimi, A., Azar, P.S., Reshadatjoo, M., Vajdi, M., Bahrami, A., Najafipour, F., Tutunchi, H., A double-blind, randomized, clinical trial of the effects of *Fumaria parviflora* supplementation on metabolic parameters, anthropometric indices and serum levels of leptin, adiponectin and resistin in patients with type 2 diabetes. *J. Biol. Regul. Homeost. Agents.*, 2023; 37: 4825-4836. DOI: 10.23812/j.biol.regul.homeost.agents.20233709.470
129. Karimi, A., Abdollahinia, E.D., Ostadrahimi, S., Vajdi, M., Mobasser, M., Bahrami, A., Tutunchi, H., Najafipour, F., Effects of hydroalcoholic extract of *Fumaria parviflora*

- Lam on gene expression and serum levels of inflammatory and oxidative stress parameters in patients with type 2 diabetes: A randomized controlled clinical trial. *J. Funct. Foods.*, 2024; 122: 106528. DOI: 10.1016/j.jff.2024.106528
130. Kooshki, F., Niazkar, H.R., Shirazi, S., Asghari Azar, V., Moghimian, M., Karimi, A., *Fumaria parviflora* improves liver damage and lipid profile changes in STZ-induced diabetic rats. *Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 2020; 24: 221-229. DOI: 10.32598/ppj.24.3.80
131. Eghdami, S., Afrashteh, F., Shojaii, A., Abolhasani, M., Motevalian, M., The therapeutic effect of alcoholic extract of *Fumaria parviflora* on high-fat diet-induced nonalcoholic fatty liver in rats: an animal experiment. *Ann. Med. Surg.*, 2024; 86: 2657-2664. DOI: 10.1097/MS9.0000000000001890
132. Arzi, A., Nazari, Z., Ahmadi Salieneh, S.V., Study of the effect of hydro alcoholic extract of *Fumaria parviflora* on carrageenan induced inflammation in male rat paw. *Jentashapir*. 2013; 4: 121-130. [ResearchGate, article in Persian]
133. Rizvi, W., Fayazuddin, M., Singh, O., Syed, S.N., Moin, S., Akhtar, K., Kumar, A., Anti-inflammatory effect of *Fumaria parviflora* leaves based on TNF- α , IL-1, IL-6 and antioxidant potential. *Avicenna J. Phytomed.*, 2017; 7: 37-45. DOI: 10.22038/ajp.2016.6955
134. Bhargava, A., Shrivastava, P., Tilwari, A., Investigation of Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Activity of *Fumaria parviflora* LAM. *J. Adv. Sci. Res.*, 2022; 13: 146-150. DOI: 10.55218/JASR.202213323
135. Lotfi Vanashi, A., Ghamari, F., Farahmand, S., Jamshidi, A., Study of antimicrobial and antioxidant effects and phytochemical characteristics of *Matricaria recutita* L, *Nigella sativa* L., *Fumaria parviflora* Lam and *Myrtus communis* L. Extracts on pathogenic bacteria from human blood and urine cultures. *Iran. J. Nutr. Sci. Food Technol.*, 2023; 18: 39-49. [Journal Website, article in Persian]
136. Naz, I., Saifullah, M.R., Ali, S., Khan, S.M., Antibacterial activity of secondary metabolites from *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. (Fumariaceae). *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res.* 2013; 23: 29-36. [ResearchGate]
137. Jameel, M., Islamuddin, M., Ali, A., Afrin, F., Ali, M., Isolation, characterization and antimicrobial evaluation of a novel compound N-octacosan 7 β ol, from *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. *BMC Complement. Altern. Med.*, 2014; 14: 98. DOI: 10.1186/1472-6882-14-98

138. Heidari, M.R., Mnadgary, A., Enayati, M., Antinociceptive effects and toxicity of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. in mice and rats. *Daru J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2004; 12: 136-140. [[ResearchGate](#)]
139. Kumar, S., Kamboj, A., Sharma, A.K., Antioxidant evaluation of ethanolic extract of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. obtained from root, stem, leaf and fruit and measurement of their total phenols and flavonoids. *Pharma Innov. J.* 2018; 7: 577-579. [[Journal Website](#)]
140. Sharma, N., Shakya, A.K., Shrivastava, S., Shukla, S., Antioxidant and Ameliorative Effect of Indian *Fumaria Parviflora* Aqueous Extract against CCl₄ induced Hepatotoxicity in Albino Rats. *J. Ayurveda Holist. Med.*, 2023; 11: 1-17. DOI: 10.70066/jahm.v11i1.625
141. Shokoohi, M., Farashah, M.S., Khaki, A., Khaki, A.A., Ouladsahebmadarek, E., Nezhad, R.A., Protective Effect of *Fumaria parviflora* Extract on Oxidative Stress and Testis Tissue Damage in Diabetic Rats. *Crescent J. Med. Biol. Sci.*, 2019; 6: 355-360. [[Journal Website](#)]
142. Al-Shaibani, I.R., Phulan, M.S., Shiekh, M., Anthelmintic activity of *Fumaria parviflora* (Fumariaceae) against gastrointestinal nematodes of sheep. *Int. J. Agric. Biol.* 2009; 11: 431-436. [[ResearchGate](#)]
143. Naz, I., Palomares-Rius, J.E., Saifullah, Blok, V., Khan, M.R., Ali, S., Ali, S., *In vitro* and *in planta* nematicidal activity of *Fumaria parviflora* (Fumariaceae) against the southern root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita*. *Plant Pathol.*, 2013; 62: 943-952. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-3059.2012.02682.x
144. Simin, A., Ghaffarifar, F., Hamid Delavari, H., Bineshian, F., Evaluation the effects of *Fumaria parviflora* aqueous extracts on *Leishmania major* in vitro and in vivo. *Pathobiol. Res.*, 2021; 23: 37-45. [[Journal Website](#), article in Persian]
145. Saleh, H.A., Ahmed, H.A., Aziz, L.A., Kareem, M., Fahmy, E.M., Obaid, R.F., AlHuchaimi, S.N., Hazim, A., Mahmood, T.A., Effects of combination of Amphotericin B and *Fumaria parviflora* ethanolic extract against *Leishmania major* and expression of miR146a-5p and miR499 levels. *Res. J. Biotechnol.*, 2022; 17: 74-78. DOI: 10.25303/1709rjbt74078
146. Qureshi, A.W., Akhtar, T., Khan, L. and Numan, M., Anti-fasciolic effect of raw seeds of *Nigella sativa*, *Fumaria parviflora* (aerial parts), in naturally infected buffaloes. *Biosci. J.* 2023; 39: e39068. DOI: 10.14393/BJ-v39n0a2023-65038

147. Naz, I., Saifullah, S., Khan, M.R., Nematicidal activity of nonacosane-10-ol and 23a-homostigmast-5-en-3 β -ol isolated from the roots of *Fumaria parviflora* (Fumariaceae). *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2013; *61*: 5689-5695. DOI: 10.1021/jf401309r
148. Dorostghoal, M., Seyyednejad, S.M., Jabari, A., Protective effects of *Fumaria parviflora* L. on lead-induced testicular toxicity in male rats. *Andrologia.*, 2014; *46*: 437-446. DOI: 10.1111/and.12100
149. Wahid, M.A., Chemical studies on *Fumaria parviflora* Lamk. I. Nonalkaloidal constituents of the plant. *Pak. J., Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961; *4*: 121-123. [Journal Website]
150. Hussain, S.F., Minard, R.D., Freyer, A.J., Shamma, M., New alkaloids from *Fumaria parviflora*. *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1981; *44*: 169-178. DOI: 10.1021/np50014a005
151. Blaskó, G., Hussain, S.F., Shamma, M., (-)-Corlumine, a new phthalideisoquinoline alkaloid from *Fumaria parviflora*. *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1981; *44*: 475-477. DOI: 10.1021/np50016a014
152. Popova, M.E, Simánek, V., Dolejs, L., Smysl, B., Preininger, V., Alkaloids from *Fumaria parviflora* and *F. kralikii*. *Planta Med.*, 1982; *45*: 120-122. DOI: 10.1055/s-2007-971259
153. Forgacs, P., Provost, J., Presence of rhoegenine in *Fumaria parviflora*. *J. Nat. Prod.* 1985; *48*: 1000-1001. DOI: 10.1021/np50042a029
154. Khalighi-Sigaroodi, F., Yazdani, D., Taghizadeh, M., Rezazadeh, S., Quantitative determination of an effective component of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. *J. Med. Plants.* 2005; *4*: 62-71. [ResearchGate, article in Persian]
155. Ashnagar, A., Naseri, N.G., Yaghoobi, M., Chemical composition of the essential oil of fumitory plant (*Fumaria parviflora* Lam) (Fineleaf fumitory) grown in Ahwaz, Iran. *Asian J. Chem.* 2007; *19*: 5336-5340. [Journal Website]
156. Jameel, M., Ali, A., Ali, M., New phytoconstituents from the aerial parts of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. *J. Adv. Pharm. Technol. Res.*, 2014; *5*: 64-69. DOI: 10.4103/2231-4040.133424
157. Modi, K., Amin, A., Shah, M., A pharmacognostical study on *Fumaria parviflora* Lamk. *J. Nat. Rem.*, 2016; *16*: 1-6. DOI: 10.18311/jnr/2016/748
158. Jameel, M., Ali, A., Ali, M., Identification of new compounds from *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. *J. Appl. Pharm. Sci.*, 2017; *7*: 53-60. DOI: 10.7324/JAPS.2017.70407
159. Farhan, M.S., Kadheem, E.J., Isolation and characterization of new flavonoids from *Fumaria parviflora* cultivated in Iraq. *J. Glob. Pharm. Technol.*, 2019; *11*: 809-816. [ResearchGate]

160. Gaind, K.N., Singla, A.K., Wallace, J.W., Flavonoid glycosides of *Kalanchoe spathulata*. *Phytochemistry.*, 1981; 20: 530-531. DOI: 10.1016/S0031-9422(00)84187-4
161. Bhargava, A., Shrivastava, P., Tilwari, A., Pharmacognostical and phytochemical investigation of *Fumaria parviflora* lam. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.*, 2021; 12: 4429-4434. DOI: 10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.12(8).4429-34
162. Singadi, R., Maste, M.M., Gharge, S., Halagali, P., Bhandurge, P., Suryawanshi, S.S., Physico-chemical investigation and characterization of *Fumaria parviflora* lam. *Int. J. Res. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, 2022; 7: 95-100. [[ResearchGate](#)]
163. Jameel, M., Ali, A. and Ali, M., Phytochemical investigation of the aerial parts of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. *J. Pharm. Biosci.*, 2014; 2: 1-8. [[ResearchGate](#)]
164. Jamshidzadeh, A., Nikmahad, H., Hepatoprotective Effects of *Fumaria parviflora* L. on CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity. *J. Med. Plants.* 2006; 5: 34-39. [[Journal Website](#), article in Persian]
165. Alqasoumi, S.I., Al-Dosari, M.S., Alsheikh, A.M., Abdel-Kader, M.S., Evaluation of the hepatoprotective effect of *Fumaria parviflora* and *Momordica halsamina* from Saudi folk medicine against experimentally induced liver injury in rats. *Res. J. Med. Plant.*, 2009; 3: 9-15. DOI: 10.3923/rjmp.2009.9.15
166. Ozaslan, M., A comparison of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. and *Momordica balsamina* Linn. hepatoprotection. *Pak. J. Biol. Sci.*, 2011; 14: 1034-5. DOI: 10.3923/pjbs.2011.1034.1035
167. Khan, H.M., Iqbal, S., Comparative Hepatoprotective Activity of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. Leaf Extract and Silymarin on Isoniazid and Rifampicin-induced Hepatotoxic Rats. *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2017; 79: 124-130. DOI: 10.4172/pharmaceutical-sciences.1000208
168. Rezaeikia, Z., Saeidi-Sar, S., Malakijoo, N., Mousavi, Z., Chemoprotective effect of *Fumaria parviflora* L. extract against vincristine induced hepatotoxicity in male rats. *Med. Sci.*, 2019; 29: 125-130. DOI: 10.29252/iau.29.2.125 [Article in Persian]
169. Muthuramu.T., Yessu, A.M., Rahman, M.U., Hepatoprotective Activity of Methanolic Extract of *Fumaria Parviflora* Against CCL4 And Att-Induced Hepatic Injuries in Rats: A Randomized Controlled Preclinical Trial. *Indo Am. J. Pharm. Res.* 2020; 10: 785-790. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3928045
170. Eghdami, S., Afrashteh, F., Shojaii, A., Abolhasani, M., Motevalian, M., The therapeutic effect of alcoholic extract of *Fumaria parviflora* on high-fat diet-induced nonalcoholic

- fatty liver in rats: an animal experiment. *Ann. Med. Surg.*, 2024; 86: 2657-2664. DOI: 10.1097/MS9.0000000000001890
171. Abdolmaleki, A., Zhaleh, M., Ghanbari, A., Rashidi, I., Jalili, C., Feizi, F., Khani Hematabadi, F., Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Fumaria parviflora* L. Can Potentially Detoxificate HepG2 Cell Line Following Carbon Tetrachloride Exposure. *J. Clin. Res. Paramed. Sci.*, 2024; 13: e149140. DOI: 10.5812/jcrps-149140
172. Ramezani, V., Shadkam, M.N., Ghiasirad, M., Ebrahimi, S., Ranjbar, A.M., *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. Aqueous Extract Versus Simethicone in the Treatment of Infantile Colic: A Prospective Randomized Clinical Trial. *Pharmacog. Res.*, 2025; 17: 867-872. DOI: 10.5530/pres.20251909
173. Rehman, N.U., Mehmood, M.H., Al-Rehaily, A.J., Mothana, R.A., Gilani, A.H., Species and tissue-specificity of prokinetic, laxative and spasmodic effects of *Fumaria parviflora*. *BMC Complement. Altern. Med.*, 2012; 12: 16. DOI: 10.1186/1472-6882-12-16
174. Akrami, R., Hashempur, M.H., Tavakoli, A., Nimrouzi, M., Sayadi, M., Roodaki, M., Roozbeh, J., Faridi, P., Effects of *Fumaria parviflora* L on uremic pruritus in hemodialysis patients: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Jundishapur J. Nat. Pharm. Prod.*, 2016; 12: e39744. DOI: 10.5812/jjnpp.39744.
175. Mehraban, L., Saeidi, N., Latifi, A., Hamed Tabar, M., Comparison of the effect of *Fumaria Parviflora* and Gabapentin in Treatment of Uremic Pruritus in Hemodialysis Patients: A Randomized Clinical Trial Study. *J. Isfahan Med. Sch.*, 2023; 40: 966-971. DOI: 10.48305/jims.v40.i697.0966 [Article in Persian]
176. Kogani, S., Roomiani, L., The effect of alcoholic extract of *Allium jesdanum*, *Tragopon caricifolus* and *Fumaria parviflora* on the shelf life of *Rutilus kutum*. *Iranian Sci. Fish. J.* 2020; 29: 93-108. DOI: 10.22092/ISFJ.2020.122453 [Article in Persian]
177. Naseri, M., Heydari Nasrabadi, M., Khodarahmi, P., Ahmadi, F., Mojibi, P., Abotalebei, H., Study of the Effect of *Fumaria parviflora* Alcoholic Extract on Spermatogenesis in Male Rats. *New Cell. Mol. Biotechnol. J.*, 2011; 1: 61-65. [Journal Website, Article in Persian]
178. Heydari Nasrabadi, M., Aboutalebi, H., Naseri, M., Effect of *Fumaria parviflora* alcoholic extract on male rat's reproductive system. *J. Med. Plants Res.* 2012; 6: 2004-2010, DOI: 10.5897/JMPR11.1732

179. Dorostghoal, M., Seyyednejad, S.M., Khajehpour, L., Jabari, A., Effects of *Fumaria parviflora* leaves extract on reproductive parameters in adult male rats. *Iran. J. Reprod. Med.*, 2013; *11*: 891-898. [[ResearchGate](#)]
180. Dolatkhah, M.A., Khezri, S., Shokoohi, M., Alihemmati, A., The effect of *Fumaria parviflora* on the expression of sexual hormones along with their receptors in testicles of adult rats induced by varicocele. *Andrologia.*, 2022; *54*: e14512. DOI: 10.1111/and.14512
181. Jowkar, F., Jamshidzadeh, A., Mirzadeh Yazdi. A., Pasalar, M., The effects of *Fumaria parviflora* L extract on chronic hand eczema: a randomized double-blind placebo controlled clinical trial. *Iran. Red Crescent Med. J.*, 2011; *13*: 824-828. [[ResearchGate](#)]
182. Siahpush, A., Moravej, M.S., Makhmalzadeh, B.S., Formulation and Evaluation of an Herbal Cream from Dry Extract of *Glycyrrhiza globra* and *Fumaria parviflora*. *Med. J. Tabriz Univ. Med. Sci.*, 2014; *36*: 40-47. [[Journal Website](#)]
183. Tajik, J., Nazifi, S., Poorzal, F., The Effects of Long-term Use of *Fumaria parviflora* extract on Some Serum Biochemical Parameters of Rats. *J. Pharmacol. Toxicol.*, 2011; *6*: 710-714. DOI: 10.3923/jpt.2011.710.714
184. Elsaid, M.B., Elnaggar, D.M., Owis, A.I., AbouZid, S.F., Eldahmy, S., Production of Isoquinoline alkaloids from the *in vitro* conserved *Fumaria parviflora* and their *in vitro* wound healing activity. *Nat. Prod. Res.*, 2021; *36*: 2575–2579. DOI: 10.1080/14786419.2021.1904401
185. Soušek, J., Guedon, D., Adam, T., Bochořáková, H., Táborská, E., Valka, I., Šimánek, V., Alkaloids and organic acids content of eight *Fumaria* species. *Phytochem. Anal.* 1999; *10*: 6-11. DOI: 10.1002/(SICI)1099-1565(199901/02)10:1<6::AID-PCA431>3.0.CO;2-0
186. Densiflorine, PubChem CID 343060, [PubChem](#)
187. Popova, M.E., Šimánek, V., Novák, J., Dolejš, L., Sedmera, P., Preininger, V., Alkaloids of *Fumaria densiflora*. *Planta Med.*, 1983; *48*: 272-274. DOI: 10.1055/s-2007-969932
188. Densiflorine, PubChem CID 177184, [PubChem](#)
189. Roni, A.H., Mortuza, G., Rozina, R., Kumar Shaha, R., Hoque, S., Kumer, A., Identification of SARS-CoV-2 inhibitors from alkaloids using molecular modeling and *in silico* approaches. *J. Med. Nanomater. Chem.*, 2023; *5*: 252-266. DOI: 10.48309/JMNC.2023.4.1

190. Fafal, T., Önür, M.A., Determination of protopine in *Fumaria densiflora* DC. by TLC-densitometric and spectrophotometric method. *J. Fac. Pharm. Ankara Univ.*, 2007; 36: 223-236. DOI: 10.1501/Eczfak_0000000538
191. Manske, R.H., The Alkaloids of Fumariaceae XVIII: *Fumaria officinalis* L. *Can. J. Res.*, 1938; 16: 438-444. DOI: 10.1139/cjr38b-054
192. Thomas, A.F., Marion, L., Manske, R.H., The Identity of Cryptocavine and Cryptopine. *Can. J. Chem.*, 1955; 33: 570-571. DOI: 10.1139/v55-067
193. Seger, C., Sturm, S., Strasser, E.M., Ellmerer, E., Stuppner, H., ¹H and ¹³C NMR signal assignment of benzyloisoquinoline alkaloids from *Fumaria officinalis* L. (Papaveraceae). *Magn. Reson. Chem.*, 2004; 42: 882-886. DOI: 10.1002/mrc.1417
194. Khamtache-Abderrahim, S., Yahiaoui, S., Otmani, A., Bachir-Bey, M., Optimization of phenolic compound recovery and antioxidant activity from *Fumaria officinalis* L. using response surface methodology. *Food Technol.*, 2021; 45: 117-133. DOI: 10.35219/foodtechnology.2021.2.08
195. Mamomadova, G., Koseoglu-Yilmaz, P., Response Surface Methodology-Based Extraction of Fumaric Acid from *Fumaria officinalis* L. and Quantification by RP-HPLC. *Biomed. Chromatogr.*, 2025; 39: e70173. DOI: 10.1002/bmc.70173
196. Ashowen Ahmoda, R., Pirković, A., Milošević, M., Marinković, A., Jovanović, A., The Impact of Various Temperatures on Polyphenol and Flavonoid Extraction from *Fumaria officinalis* Herba. *Eng. Proceed.*, 2025; 99: 15. DOI: 10.3390/engproc2025099015
197. Bhargava, A., Shrivastava, P., Tilwari, A., HPTLC analysis of *Fumaria parviflora* (Lam.) methanolic extract of whole plant. *Futur. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2021; 7: 1. DOI: 10.1186/s43094-020-00150-x
198. Hajjaj, B., El Oualkadi, A., Tantaoui, H., Chentouf, M., Effect of Florasulam and 2,4-D on Fineleaf Fumitory (*Fumaria parviflora* Lam.) Infestation in Wheat Crop. *Arch. Curr. Res. Int.*, 2019; 19: 1–5. DOI: 10.9734/acri/2019/v19i130150
199. Tashakorizadeh, M., Vahabi, M.R., Golkar, P., Mahdavian, K., The effect of drought stress and copper element on some vegetative traits, essential oil and copper concentration in *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. *J. Plant Proc. Funct.*, 2021; 10: 1-20. [Journal Website, article in Persian]
200. Tashakorizadeh, M., Vahabi, M.R., Golkar, P., Mahdavian, K., The singular and combined effects of drought and copper stresses on the morphological traits, photosynthetic pigments, essential oils yield and copper concentration of *Fumaria*

- parviflora* Lam. *Ind. Crops Prod.*, 2022; 177: 114517. DOI: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2021.114517
201. Tashakorizadeh, M., Golkar, P., Vahabi, M.R., Ghorbanpour, M., Physiological and biochemical mechanisms of grain yield loss in fumitory (*Fumaria parviflora* Lam.) exposed to copper and drought stress. *Sci. Rep.*, 2023; 13: 19308. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-023-46587-x
202. Tashakorizadeh, M., Golkar, P., Vahabi, M.R., Effects of zone, drought and copper stresses and their interactions on some biochemical traits and grain yield of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. *Environ. Stress. Crop Sci.*, 2025; 18: 315-335. DOI: 10.22077/escs.2024.7167.2263
203. Oza, C., Method Development and Verification of Assay of Simethicone in Simethicone Soft Gel Capsule in the Form of Polydimethylsiloxane by FT-IR. *Int. J. Adv. Pharm. Sci. Res.*, 2025; 5: 5216493. DOI: 10.54105/ijapsr.C4070.05030425
204. Metcalf, T.J., Irons, T.G., Sher, L.D., Young, P.C., Simethicone in the treatment of infant colic: a randomized, placebo-controlled, multicenter trial. *Pediatrics.*, 1994; 94: 29-34. DOI: 10.1542/peds.94.1.29
205. Evans, C., Lorentz, W.P., Efficacy and Safety of a Colic Relief Remedy in Infantile Colic. *Glob. Pediatr. Health.*, 2022; 9: 1-7. DOI: 10.1177/2333794X221100810
206. Mohammadi, S.S., Ghasemi, N., Ramezani, M., Bio-fabrication of silver nanoparticles using naturally available wild herbaceous plant and its antibacterial activity. *J. Med. Pharm. Chem. Res.*, 2020; 2: 87-102. [Journal Website]
207. Haji, A.A., Abduljabar, R.S., Yasin, S.A., Omar, Z.A., Ahmed, H.A., Assiri, M.A., Ali, G.A., Green Synthesis of Magnetite Nanoparticles Mediated *Fumaria officinalis* L. Plant as Sustainable and Renewable Adsorbing Materials. *Separations.*, 2023; 10: 518. DOI: 10.3390/separations10090518
208. Li, C., Zhang, Y., Li, M., Zhang, H., Zhu, Z., Xue, Y., *Fumaria officinalis*-assisted synthesis of manganese nanoparticles as an anti-human gastric cancer agent. *Arabian J. Chem.*, 2021; 14: 103309. DOI: 10.1016/j.arabjc.2021.103309
209. Yang, X., Mo, W., Shi, Y., Fang, X., Xu, Y., He, X., Xu, Y., *Fumaria officinalis*-loaded chitosan nanoparticles dispersed in an alginate hydrogel promote diabetic wounds healing by upregulating VEGF, TGF- β , and b-FGF genes: A preclinical investigation. *Heliyon.* 2023; 9: e17704. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17704

210. Huang, Y., Zhu, C., Xie, R., Ni, M., Green synthesis of nickel nanoparticles using *Fumaria officinalis* as a novel chemotherapeutic drug for the treatment of ovarian cancer, *J. Exper. Nanosci.*, 2021; 16: 368-381. DOI: 10.1080/17458080.2021.1975037
211. Zou, M., Zhong, Z., Wen, C., Characterization and anti-acute myeloid leukemia and anti-acute T cell leukemia properties of zinc nanoparticles synthesized by a green approach for bioremediation applications. *Arch. Med. Sci.*, 2021; 140295. DOI: 10.5114/aoms/140295
212. Hayat, K., Din, I.U., Alam, K., Khan, F.U., Khan, M., Mohamed, H.I., Green synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles using plant extracts of *Fumaria officinalis* and *Peganum harmala* and their antioxidant and antibacterial activities. *Biomass Convers. Biorefin.*, 2025; 15: 9565-9579. DOI: 10.1007/s13399-024-05804-x
213. Dousti B, Nabipour F, Hajiamraei A. Green synthesis of silver nanoparticle by using the aqueous extract of *Fumaria Parviflora* and investigation of their antibacterial and antioxidant activities. *Razi J. Med. Sci.*, 2019; 26: 105-117. [Journal Website, article in Persian]
214. Sattari, R., Khayati, G.R., Hoshyar, R., Biosynthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles capped by biomolecules by *Fumaria parviflora* extract as green approach and evaluation of their cytotoxicity against human breast cancer MDA-MB-468 cell lines. *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, 2020; 24: 122438. DOI: 10.1016/j.matchemphys.2019.122438
215. Fakharzadeh, M., Fazljoo, S.E., Biosynthesis of Silver Nanoparticles Using Barley straw and *Fumaria parviflora* extract: Optimization of Synthesis, Evaluating of Nanoparticles Stability, Antibacterial Activities. *Bio. Nano. Sci.*, 2024; 14: 318-336. DOI: 10.1007/s12668-023-01242-7
216. Razavi, R., Kenari, R.E., Antioxidant evaluation of *Fumaria parviflora* L. extract loaded nanocapsules obtained by green extraction methods in oxidative stability of sunflower oil. *Food Meas.*, 2021; 15: 2448-2457. DOI: 10.1007/s11694-021-00837-6
217. Simin, A., Ghaffarifar, F., Delavari, H., Dayer, M.S., Hamidianfar, N., Baghkhani, F., In vitro and in vivo effects of ethanolic extract of *Fumaria parviflora* Lam. embedded in chitosan nanoparticles against *Leishmania major*. *Acta Parasitol.* 2024; 69: 628-638. DOI: 10.1007/s11686-023-00784-w
218. Dousti, B., Habibi, A., Nabipor, F., Biosynthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles using *Fumaria parviflora* extract and evaluation of their antibacterial and antioxidant activities. *BioTechnologia.*, 2021; 102: 65-73. DOI: 10.5114/bta.2021.103763